

Elementary Quantum Gravity Model to explain Dark Matter and Dark Energy as well as Nuclear and Electrodynamic Forces

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- Preprint -

Abstract

Although gravitation as described by Newton is an elementary force, gravity constant G is still the least precisely known in physics. In the 20th century observations on galaxy rotation showed significant violation of Newton's law, leading to ongoing search for Dark Matter (DM) versus modified Newton dynamics. In addition, at the end of the last century observation of accelerated expansion for the Universe raised the issue of missing Dark Energy (DE).

In this work I derive an analytical Elementary Quantum Gravity Model (EQGM) describing quantum nature of gravitation for the Universe and do find qualitative and quantitative agreement with astronomical observations. It leads to a zero-point gravitational acceleration that can explain observed galaxy rotation, as well as observed DM and DE effects, and accelerated expansion of the Universe in line with the current Standard Model of Cosmology.

Based on this new model, comprising fluctuations with quantum energy states and quantum exchange particles dubbed “ghotons”, discrete gravitational quantum effects between mass objects are proposed. Moreover, a minimum particle mass, granularity of time and entropy for the Universe are derived and discussed. With this, also an explanation approach for the redshift quantization phenomenon is given.

It is found that gravitation as such can be described out of quantum mechanical uncertainty based on inertia, hence also explaining the corresponding equivalence principle. Attractive and repulsive action is also shown as being immanent in the Klein-Gordon and Schrödinger equations for particle quantum systems.

Moreover, the EQGM can serve to describe energy levels found in atomic nuclei. In addition, unification of quantum gravitation and nuclear force within the deuteron is suggested, due to the identity of pion and photon being found.

Finally, the Coulombian electrodynamic force can be unified in the EQGM as a degenerated multi-particle quantum gravitational effect, thus confirming long-standing Large Number Hypotheses for the Universe.

Key words: quantum gravity, quantum cosmology, dark matter, dark energy, alternative gravity theories, nuclear physics, quantum electrodynamics, theory of everything

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I. INTRODUCTION

To date the gravitational force between two mass objects is described by Newton's law [1] as first confirmed in measurement by Henry Cavendish in the 18th century [2]:

$$F_g = \frac{m_1 m_2 G}{r^2}. \quad (1)$$

Since then, it has been tried to describe its nature, leading to general relativity theory of A. Einstein in the 20th century, as a geometric approach on space-time [3]. Although discovered more than three centuries ago, G is still the most imprecisely determined constant in physics [4], with $G = 6.6743 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{kg}^{-1} \text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-2}$ and a relative uncertainty of $2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$.

Moreover, despite intense and diverse attempts to link gravity and quantum mechanics over the last decades, leading to several competing approaches, none of them proves so far to resolve major inconsistencies qualitatively and quantitatively observed with gravitation in nature. Overviews reflecting the state of research can be found for example in [5], [6], [7].

With advancement in astronomical measurement techniques, it was found from observational statistics of galaxies, that their rotation does not follow the Newton law of gravitation in the outer regime, since forces calculated are too low to explain the higher observed rotational velocities [8]. To solve this issue, at least two directions of research are still followed: The search for DM, to cause an on top gravitational effect in Newton's law, versus modified newton dynamics, which so far is empirical guessing to fit to the observed behavior of galaxies [9].

Even worse, at the end of the 20th century observations led to the conclusion that expansion of the Universe as described by Edwin Hubble is accelerating [10], contradicting the believe that gravitation slows down and would stop its inflation. This leads to search for a missing DE required, being multiples larger than gravitational energy attached to visible matter in the Universe but needs to be in line with the observed Standard Model of Cosmology [11].

In this article a model to gain new insights into DM and DE, as well as on the nature of gravitation, is derived and applied.

I follow the approach, that it should be as simple as possible, only as complicated as necessary, and in line with proven observations and physical models.

¹See Appendix A for derivation of a relativistic Heisenberg uncertainty as applied here.

II. ELEMENTARY QUANTUM GRAVITY MODEL (EQGM)

Following the aim of this article, I use proven quantum mechanical laws and models to compose an Elementary Quantum Gravity Model (EQGM). This means developing an analogue gravity model out of atom and solid-state physics, practically following an idea as proposed for example in [12].

A. Quantum mechanical approach

To introduce quantum mechanics, I start with a one-dimensional Heisenberg uncertainty [13] with $x = r$ to address a radially symmetric Universe and adapt it with the Lorentz factor γ to consider relativistic effects¹. Hence, the variance of momentum and location, as well as of energy and time for a mass object all must have non-zero values. With the reduced Planck quantum of action $\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}$ and $h = 6.62607015 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{J}$ it writes:

$$\sigma_p \sigma_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_W \sigma_t \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (2)$$

I apply this to a mass object (mo) in the Universe (U). The radius of the Universe is confining the location of the object in a gravitational potential well, while the time uncertainty is related to the time in the Universe. In the relativistic view, in principle its energy uncertainty can be rooted in its kinetic energy or in its rest energy.

1. Kinetic energy uncertainty

For the first case, using the kinetic energy equivalent for the object from the gravitational potential, the uncertainties are set up as equations, anticipating minimum energy possible:

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{2} \sigma_{WU} &= -W_{\text{pot}} = \int_{\infty}^{R_U} \frac{m M_U G}{r^2} dr = \\ &= \frac{m M_U G}{R_U} = W_{\text{kin}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{and hence } \sqrt{2} \sigma_{tU} = \frac{2 R_U \hbar}{\gamma m M_U G}. \quad (3)$$

The zero-level for total energy of the mass m is set at infinity. The momentum uncertainty is written up by the mass and velocity uncertainties, with the latter one given by the product of acceleration and time uncertainty:

$$\sqrt{2} \sigma_{pU} = \sqrt{2} (\sigma_{mU} \sigma_{aU} \sigma_{tU}) = m_0 \gamma a_U t_U, \text{ and}$$

$$\sqrt{2}\sigma_{xU} = R_U. \quad (4)$$

With this we gain:

$$a_U \geq \frac{M_U G}{2R_U^2}, \quad (5)$$

an inertial acceleration that equals gravitational acceleration due to the equivalence principle, in case of no other forces involved. The Lorentz factor results from the calculated value for σ_{WU} , since kinetic energy shows to have the same value as the rest energy of mass:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c_0^2}}} = 1 + \frac{\sigma_{WU}}{m_0 c_0^2} = 2. \quad (5a)$$

For the radius² of the Universe I assume $R_U = 4.413 \cdot 10^{26} m$. Consecutively, for the mass³ it results $M_U = 5.899 \cdot 10^{53} kg$.

With this a zero-point acceleration for any mass that cannot be underrun is found:

$$g_{zp} = a_U = 1.026 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2}. \quad (6)$$

This value is in the range of what has been empirically found as a_0 at around $1 \dots 1.2 \cdot 10^{-10} m/s^2$, the threshold value to invalidity of Newton's law in galaxy observations [9], [15].

To formulate the EQGM I will use the fundamental Planck-units, as introduced in the year 1899 for basic physical quantities [16]. They are composed only of key constants determining relativistic electrodynamics (speed of light $c_0 = 2.99792458 \cdot 10^8 m/s$), gravitation (gravity constant G), and quantum mechanics (quantum of action \hbar). Furthermore Planck-units describe a limit for quantum effects in gravitation, while Planck-mass can be found in setting the Schwarzschild perimeter of a black hole to be equal to its Compton wavelength [17]: $2\pi r_s = \lambda_C$ with $r_s = \frac{m_{Pl} G}{c_0^2}$ and $\lambda_C = \frac{\hbar}{m_{Pl} c_0}$, yielding:

$$m_{Pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c_0}{G}} = 2.178 \cdot 10^{-8} kg. \quad \text{Moreover Planck-length defined as: } l_{Pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c_0^3}} = 1.616 \cdot 10^{-35} m,$$

results to Planck-time for light traveling along it: $t_{Pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c_0^5}} = 5.391 \cdot 10^{-44} s$. The Planck-energy exhibits a value same as the rest energy for Planck-mass: $W_{Pl} =$

$$\sqrt{\frac{\hbar c_0^5}{G}} = m_{Pl} c_0^2 = 1.956 \cdot 10^9 J.$$

With this the Heisenberg uncertainty for mass objects in the Universe can be normalized to Planck-units, while introducing a parameter $\xi > 0$ as scale factor:

$$(m_{Pl} \xi \gamma) \sigma_a \left(\frac{t_{Pl}}{\xi} \right) \sigma_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (7)$$

From this the same value for the zero-point acceleration as already calculated above does result:

$$a_U \geq \frac{c_0^2}{2R_U} = 1.026 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2}. \quad (8)$$

Comparing with Eq. (5), it is found:

$$G = \frac{R_U c_0^2}{M_U}. \quad (9)$$

The perspective is, that the gravity ‘‘constant’’ appears as a parameter. With this and Eq. (3) the minimum kinetic energy for a mass in the Universe results to:

$$W_{kUmin} = m_0 c_0^2. \quad (10)$$

This result is also found from the uncertainty relations. Although the value is the same as for the rest energy of mass, it is a kinetic energy appearing on top, since being linked to momentum in the uncertainty relations:

$$\sqrt{2}\sigma_{WU} = m_{mo} \gamma \sqrt{2}\sigma_a R_U = m_0 c_0^2 = W_{kUmin}. \quad (11)$$

2. Rest energy uncertainty

For the second case that rest energy fluctuations would make up energy uncertainty, the results are the same as in the section given above, since kinetic and rest energy have been found to exhibit identical values. The difference in derivation required is that σ_m is the fluctuating uncertainty with the effective average being equal to mass observed, that thus would have no fixed value over time. Consequently, acceleration σ_a must be replaced by the fixed value of g_{zp} instead:

$$\sqrt{2}\sigma_{WU} = \sqrt{2}\sigma_{mmo} \gamma g_{zp} R_U = m_0 c_0^2 = W_{kin}. \quad (12)$$

B. Gravitational energy potential of the Universe

The simplified model for the gravitational energy potential for a mass in the Universe consists of two regimes⁴: Outside for $R > R_U$ in the vacuum it is

² This exact value is the result of the model derived in this work as described in section II.C. The value deviates only -0.73% from what was given as $4.413 \cdot 10^{26} m$, equaling 46.65 billion lightyears and 14,300 Mpc , in [14].

³ As part of the problem with DM and DE, the value for the mass of the Universe cannot be exactly known a priori. An explanation for why I can assume the mass of the Universe as stated here is given in sections III.B and III.C.

⁴ Refer to section II.C below for a discussion of this simplified approach when compared to a Schwarzschild solution based on the

hyperbolic, as given in Eq. (3).

Inside for $R \leq R_U$ one can assume a homogeneous mass density which is for a mass in intergalactic space, distant from any massive mass objects and thus facing a parabolic potential:

$$W_{gUi} = \int_{R_U}^R \frac{mMUG(r/R_U)^3}{r^2} dr = \frac{m_0 c_0^2}{2} \left[\left(\frac{R}{R_U} \right)^2 - 1 \right]. \quad (13)$$

Thus, the kinetic energy gained by a mass object falling in the negative gravitational energy potential straight into the homogeneous Universe is $(1/2)m c_0^2$ at maximum on top of the zero-point energy.

Figure 1 shows the combined gravitational potential for a Planck-mass.

FIG. 1. The potential of gravitational energy W_{gpot} [J] for an object with Planck-mass in a homogeneous static Universe depending on its radial position r [m]. The zero-point energy level at $r = R_U$ is indicated by the dotted-dashed line.

In case of inhomogeneous mass distribution, including singularities, the kinetic energy of a mass within the Universe will increase beyond the factor 3/2 of the value of its rest energy⁵.

C. Quantization of gravitation

To describe gravitational quantization for a mass object, this needs also to be done for two cases: First for the hyperbolic potential describing inhomogeneous mass densities and singularities, and second for parabolic potentials describing homogeneous mass densities.

general relativity theory.

⁵ From the perspective within the Universe these energies cannot be perceived directly for mass objects in proximity since they are experiencing the same gravitational and inflationary accelerations, being equal to inertial acceleration due to the equivalence principle.

⁶ The Virial theorem $W_{kin} = -\frac{1}{2}W_{pot}$ for non-relativistic Coulombian and gravitational closed systems does directly result from the equivalence of centripetal and attractive Coulombian / gravitational forces imposed on the mass object m in the Bohr model.

1. Inhomogeneous mass density constellations

To describe interaction between two mass objects I use an analogy to proven laws from atom and solid-state physics, namely the quantum model for an electron in the Coulomb potential of a hydrogen atom. This has been found by N. Bohr more than a century ago and explains the stability of atoms due to finite and quantized energy levels, despite a hyperbolic singularity potential [18]. Bohr's postulate:

$$pr \equiv \hbar n, \text{ with: } n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (14)$$

is a discretized Heisenberg uncertainty, equaling integer multiples of Planck's quantum of action with the product of momentum and location.

i) Non-relativistic approach

With this, quantized kinetic energies and radii were obtained for the electron in the hydrogen atom:

$$W_{ckin} = \frac{q^2}{8\pi\epsilon_0 r_B n^2} \text{ and the Bohr radius:}$$

$$r_B = \frac{4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar^2}{m_e q^2}. \quad (15)$$

I transfer this to a model for gravitation between mass objects. Since Coulomb and gravitation force laws are similar related to the formula above, except for a factor $G/(4\pi\epsilon_0)$ and charge q^2 to be replaced by the product of mass m and M , we gain for the gravitational kinetic energy⁶:

$$W_{gkin} = \frac{mMG}{2r_{gB} n^2} = \frac{m^3 M^2 G^2}{2\hbar^2 n^2} = -\frac{1}{2}W_{gpot}, \quad (16)$$

and a "gravitational Bohr radius":

$$r_{gB} = \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2 M G} = \frac{\lambda_C^2 M_U}{R_U M}, \quad (17)$$

with: $r_U = n^2 r_{gB}$. In this $\lambda_C = \frac{\hbar}{m c_0}$ is the reduced Compton wavelength for the mass object m , meaning that its rest energy equals the energy of a matter wave with this wavelength. This is also known as minimum spatial extend for which a reasonable radius of the mass object m can be defined due to quantum uncertainty.

Reformulating Eq. (16), I find an expression that can be interpreted as containing a quantum exchange

particle I call “ghoton” (Gh):

$$W_{gkin} = \frac{M^2(m_0c_0^2)^3}{2M_U^2n_{Gr}^2W_{GhU}^2} = W_{Gr}(n_{Gr}) \quad (18)$$

This particle is in analogy to a photon and it seems to be moving with the speed of light, defined as:

$$W_{GhU} = W_{Gh}(R_U) = \frac{\hbar c_0}{R_U} = 7.218 \cdot 10^{-53} J \quad (19)$$

In Eq. (18) the ghton can also be related directly to the mass object m attracted by a mass M within the Universe with:

$$W_{Gh}(r_g) = \frac{\hbar c_0}{R_U \frac{M}{M_U}} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{\left[\frac{GM}{2}\right]} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{\left[\frac{r_g}{2}\right]} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{r_g} \quad , \quad (20)$$

leading to:

$$W_{gkin} = \frac{W_0(m_0)^3}{2n_{Gr}^2W_{Gh}(r_g(M))^2} \quad (21)$$

In Eq. (20) the denominator is half of the Schwarzschild radius for a non-rotating black hole made up by mass M , or the Schwarzschild aka gravitational radius for a rotating black hole [24]. Furthermore Eq. (11) divided by the speed of light yields the de Broglie [26] expression with the gravitational perimeter of a rotating black hole as the wavelength.

For the quantized energy state levels arising from Eq. (18), I call these quasi-particles “gravons” (Gr), with n_{Gr} the gravon quantum number. This is in analogy to the phonon, the quasi-particle for the energy states of collective atom oscillations in solid-state crystals [19].

The corresponding de Broglie wavelength of the ghton for the Universe is $\lambda_{Gh} = 2\pi R_U = 2.752 \cdot 10^{27} m$ with a frequency of $f_{Gh} = 1.089 \cdot 10^{-19} Hz$, thus can be thought of as spanning along the perimeter of the Universe.

For the quantum number, e.g. for a Planck-mass at the boarder of the Universe⁷, we can calculate using Eq. (17) while setting $r_U := R_U$:

$$n_{Grmax} = \frac{R_U m_{Pl} c_0}{\hbar} = \frac{R_U}{\lambda_C(m_{Pl})} = 2.710 \cdot 10^{61} . \quad (22)$$

In the three-dimensional spherical Bohr atom model, each energy state n for fermions along the radial n_{GrR} quantum number is degenerated along the two angular quantum numbers $n_{Gr\phi}$, $n_{Gr\theta}$, and the spin degeneracy $g_s = 2$ according to the Pauli principle. The degeneration comprises a maximum of $2n^2$ states,

⁷ Assuming that the gravitational potential of the Universe in a simplified perspective can be described by the hyperbolic formula for a mass object at its boarder.

hence resulting to a total number of available states with:

$$n_{as} = 2n^3 . \quad (23)$$

Thus N identical mass objects m confined in a sphere with radius R will occupy the states up to the highest non-relativistic kinetic energy known as the Fermi energy [19] adding on top of the zero-point energy level with:

$$W_F = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{3\pi^2 N}{(4/3)\pi R^3} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} . \quad (24)$$

ii) Special relativity approach

Within the relativistic regime for objects where $v \ll c_0$ is no longer valid, the consideration of the position of an observer in terms of different inertial systems is required. Furthermore, propagation of the gravitational interaction effect is limited by the speed of light. Thus, there is a tension between the perspective of time-independent, non-local quantum states valid for the entire Universe and relativistic local inertial systems, which is not resolved to date in general and hence also effects the view on black holes [30]. However, considerations must at least make a conscious choice of the observational positions according to the questions to be answered. With this, two different perspectives shall be described here: An observer being far away from the interacting mass objects ($m; M$) called inertial system (U), and an observer co-moving with the perspective of mass object m in an inertial system (mo).

Aiming for an initial insight into the nature of relativistic gravitational quantization I will use a simple modified Newtonian approach enriched with effects from the Special Relativity Theory (SRT). Then, I will compare this to a General Relativity Theory (GRT) approach based on the Schwarzschild solution in the next sub-section.

Starting from the Bohr model Eq. (14), that remains valid also in the relativistic case for the mass object in its co-moving inertial system (mo) with $m_{mo} = m_0$ it is:

$$(m_{mo}v)r_{mo} \equiv \hbar n,$$

$$\text{resulting into: } r_{mo} = \frac{\hbar n}{m_0 v} . \quad (25)$$

In this the momentum in the inertial system co-moving with the mass object (mo) shows no increase of inertia or length contraction of the radius for the respective

circular track for mass m around mass object M .

However, a relativistic Bohr postulate must be set up for an observer in the inertial system of the Universe (U), and there it needs to consider the observed increase of inertia: $m_U = m_{mo}\gamma$ and length contraction: $r_U = r_{mo}\gamma^{-1}$ of the radius when comparing to the inertial system (mo)⁸. This leads to the relativistic momentum for the mass object m based on the relative velocity v between the inertial systems (U) and (mo) [31] as:

$p_U r_U = (m_0 \gamma v) r_U \equiv \hbar n$, resulting into:

$$r_U = \frac{\hbar n}{m_0 \gamma v}. \quad (26)$$

With this the quantization of angular momentum observed in the inertial system (U) in the relativistic case is the same as the quantization for the non-relativistic case as γ cancels out.

This is applied to the balance of Coulombian versus centrifugal forces for an electron in an atom with atomic number Z :

$$F_C = \frac{Zq^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r_U^2} \equiv \frac{m_0 \gamma v_U^2}{r_U} = F_c, \quad (27)$$

while considering relativistic velocity and kinetic energy as $v = c_0 \sqrt{1 - \gamma^{-2}}$ and $W_{kCr} = m c_0^2 (\gamma - 1)$, yielding a bi-quadratic solution for the Lorentz factor as:

$$\gamma_U = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{Z\alpha_C}{n}\right)^2}}, \quad (28)$$

containing the Sommerfeld fine-structure constant $\alpha_C = \frac{q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar c_0}$. As can be seen from the radicand, a stable ground-state $n = 1$, and thus stable atom, can only be achieved for $Z < 1/\alpha_C \approx 137$, otherwise the inner electron in the shell will be captured by the atomic nucleus.

Analogous, I apply the same approach to the gravitational force between two mass objects (m, M), again for an inertial system in the Universe (U) far away from these mass objects as:

$$F_g = \frac{(m_0 \gamma_U m_0)(M \gamma_U M_0)G}{r_U^2} \equiv \frac{(m_0 \gamma_U m_0)v_U^2}{r_U} = F_c, \quad (29)$$

with γ_{UX_0} the respective Lorentz factors related to the mass objects in the inertial system (U). For the case

$m \ll M$ it is $\gamma_{UM_0} \rightarrow 1$, and with this the resulting bi-quadratic equation yields:

$$\gamma_{Um_0} = \frac{\sqrt{2n\lambda_C(m)}}{r_S(M)} \sqrt{1 - \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{r_S(M)}{n\lambda_C(m)}\right)^2}}, \quad (30)$$

with $r_S(M) = \frac{2MG}{c_0^2}$ being the Schwarzschild radius of mass object M .

In analogy to the relativistic Coulombian Bohr atom model, real-valued solutions indicating stable quantum states are only found if $r_S(M) \leq n\lambda_C(m)$. Otherwise, all quantum numbers causing a negative radicand in Eq. (30) are located within the black hole defined by the Schwarzschild radius of the mass object M . Thus, a mass object m approaching will fall into it. Further reformulating Eq. (30) yields:

$$\gamma_{Um_0} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{r_S(M)}{n\lambda_C(m)}\right)^2}}}, \quad (31)$$

showing that the maximum Lorentz factor to be observed in the inertial system (U) is $\gamma_{Um_0max} \rightarrow \sqrt{2}$.

For the radius in the inertial system (U) with Eq. (29) and Eq. (31) it is yielded:

$$r_U = \frac{r_S(M)}{1 - \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{r_S(M)}{n\lambda_C(m)}\right)^2}}, \quad (32)$$

delivering that the minimum observable radius for mass object m in the inertial system (U) is the Schwarzschild radius of mass object M , while the minimum observable quantum number is the integer number rounded up as:

$$n_U \geq n_{Umin} = \left\lceil \frac{r_S(M)}{\lambda_C(m)} \right\rceil \quad (33)$$

For the radius in the inertial system (mo) co-moving with the mass object m the value of the minimum radius from the inertial system (U) based on Eq. (32) will be length-contracted by $\gamma_{Um_0max} \rightarrow \sqrt{2}$ as derived above.

However, in the inertial system (mo) the mass object further falling into the black hole will decrease its quantum number while its minimum spatial extend based on Eq. (25) due to $v \rightarrow c_0$ is converging towards its reduced Compton wavelength, leading to

⁸ As it is confirmed by experiment in circular particle accelerators, for an electrically charged mass in its balance of magnetic Lorentz and centrifugal forces in the inertial system of the Universe, mass inertia increase by the Lorentz factor must be considered. Hence this will also apply adopting to the balance between gravitational and centrifugal force:

$$F_g = \frac{m\gamma MG}{r_U^2} \equiv \frac{m\gamma v_U^2}{r_U} = F_c.$$

quantization of the radius as $r_{mo} \rightarrow n\lambda_C(m)$. For $n_U < \frac{r_S(M)}{\lambda_C(m)}$ the mass object m will be no longer observable in the inertial system (U) since it moves behind the event horizon of the black hole.

Thus, for the mass object in the co-moving inertial system (mo) falling into the black hole, the energy will be:

$$W_{krghmo} = -W_{potrg} \rightarrow \frac{m_0(M\gamma_{mo}M_0)G}{n\lambda_C(m_0)}, \quad (34)$$

while for this and $m \ll M$ the Lorentz factor for the mass objects approaching each other is:

$$\gamma_{moM_0} \rightarrow 1 + \frac{W_{krghmo}}{m_0c_0^2} \quad (35)$$

Inserting Eq. (35) into Eq. (34) yields:

$$W_{krghmo} \rightarrow \frac{m_0c_0^2}{\frac{n\lambda_C(m_0)}{r_S(M)/2} - 1} = \frac{W_0(m_0)^2M}{nW_{GhU}M_U - W_0(m_0)M} \quad (36)$$

This means, that in the inertial system (mo) the kinetic energy will reach a finite discrete maximum for the quantum number being the integer round-up as:

$$n_{momin} = \left\lceil \frac{r_S(M)}{2\lambda_C(m_0)} \right\rceil = \frac{n_{Umin}}{2} \quad (37)$$

This maximum will increase with the value of the Schwarzschild radius and hence mass M and may reach values $\gamma_{moM_0} \gg 1$.

As can be seen from Eq. (36) for the case:

$$M < \frac{W_{GhU}M_U}{W_0(m_0)} = \frac{M_U}{n_{Grmax}(m_0)} \quad (38)$$

the ground-state will be located outside the Schwarzschild radius, i.e. the mass object m will not fall behind the event horizon but orbit around mass object M . For $M \ll \frac{M_U}{n_{Grmax}(m_0)}$ it is:

$$W_{krghmo} \cong \frac{W_0(m_0)^2 M}{nW_{GhU} M_U} \quad (39)$$

In the other case ($M > \frac{M_U}{n_{Grmax}(m_0)}$), from the mathematical point of view, if the quantum number would be decreased below n_{momin} , negative kinetic energies would be calculated, meaning a “repulsive gravitational force”⁹ converging towards the ground-state $n \rightarrow 1$ and $W_{krghmo} \rightarrow -m_0c_0^2$. This would result in the mass object to stay in the energetic

⁹ This could be speculated to go hand in hand with the repulsive nuclear force between elementary mass objects – see also section III.I in this work – but this is not followed up here.

¹⁰ In the inertial system (mo) co-moving with the falling mass object the velocity is zero by definition ($v_{mo} \equiv 0$; $\gamma_{mo} \equiv 0$), and the radial length in (mo) is contracted as given in Eq. (19) with $r_{mo} = r_U\gamma^{-1}$ as compared to the length in the inertial system of the Universe (U). Thus, interpreting the ratio of r_{mo}/r as a velocity higher than the speed of light for the mass object is not a valid perspective.

minimum achieved at n_{momin} and only occupy higher energy states at lower or higher quantum numbers, if required by the Fermi-Dirac statistics for multiple identical fermions. However, this scenario is speculative and needs further study elsewhere.

In the non-relativistic regime for $n \rightarrow \infty$ and hence $\gamma_{Umo} \rightarrow 1$ the kinetic energy in the inertial system of the Universe (U) based on the first two terms of a Taylor series approximation from Eq. (31) converges to the expression of the non-relativistic gravitational Bohr model as given by Eq. (18):

$$W_{knrUmo} = m_0c_0^2(\gamma_{Umo} - 1) \rightarrow \frac{M^2(m_0c_0^2)^3}{2M_U^2n^2W_{GhU}^2} \quad (40)$$

Based on the Taylor series approach also for the radius applied to Eq. (32) in the non-relativistic regime it can be shown that the approximation is the non-relativistic gravitational Bohr expression from Eq. (17):

$$r_U = \frac{r_S(M)}{1 - \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{r_S(M)}{n\lambda_C(m_0)}\right)^2}} \rightarrow \frac{n^2\hbar^2}{m_0^2MG}, \text{ for: } n, r_U \rightarrow \infty \quad (41)$$

To summarize, the relativistic quantum gravity model reflects known black hole characteristics, but leads to finite, discrete maximum energies acquired by mass objects attracted by the black hole, avoiding singularities.

iii) General relativity approach

To derive a quantum gravity solution based on the General Relativity Theory (GRT) I start from the Schwarzschild solution for a mass object m attracted by a point-like mass object M as described in [32] on page 663: From the perspective of the mass m in the inertial system (mo), it takes the time:

$$\tau(r_{mo}, M) = \frac{\pi r_{mo}}{2 c_0} \left(\frac{r_{mo}}{r_S(M)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (42)$$

to fall from radius r_{mo} to radius zero¹⁰. Rearranging and comparing to the general formula for an object to move a distance r_{mo} it is:

$$r_{mo} = \tau \left[\frac{2c_0}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{r_S(M)}{r_{mo}}} \right] = \int_0^\tau v(t) dt \quad (43)$$

Considering this velocity in the inertial system of the Universe (U) with the approach from subsection above

and Eqs. (25) and (26) giving $r_U = r_{mo}\gamma_U$ it is:

$$v_U = \frac{2c_0}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{r_S(M)}{r_{mo}\gamma_U}}, \quad (44)$$

With $r_{mo} = \frac{\hbar n}{mv}$ from Eq. (19) and $v = c_0\sqrt{1 - \gamma_U^{-2}}$ it results:

$$\gamma_U = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{4r_S(M)m_0c_0\sqrt{1-\gamma_U^{-2}}}{\pi^2\hbar n\gamma_U}}}, \quad \text{which after several}$$

reformulations and solving a bi-quadratic equation delivers:

$$\gamma_U = \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{4r_S(M)}{\pi^2 n \lambda_C}\right)^2} \quad (45)$$

With this the kinetic energy for the ultra-relativistic case with $n \rightarrow 1$ results to:

$$W_{krU} \rightarrow \frac{4}{\pi^2} \frac{W_0(m_0)^2}{W_{GhUn}} \frac{M}{M_U}, \quad (46)$$

which is differing from the SRT solution in Eq. (39) only by the first product term due to the GRT being defined on spherical length scales (i.e. quadratic length scale) instead of a one-dimensional length scale in SRT.

For the non-relativistic case $n \rightarrow \infty$ Eq. (45) can be approximated by a Taylor series considering the first derivation term only that delivers:

$$W_{knrU} = \left(\frac{4}{\pi^2} \frac{W_0(m_0)}{W_{GhUn}}\right)^2 W_0(m_0), \quad (47)$$

which deviates by a factor $(16/\pi^4)$ from the non-relativistic solution as given in Eq. (18), again because of differing length scales in SRT and GRT.

Obviously, for $r_S \gg \lambda_C$ and small quantum numbers the ultra-relativistic case with $v \rightarrow c_0$ yields:

$$r_{mo} \cong n\lambda_C \quad (48)$$

With feeding γ_U from Eq. (45) into Eq. (25) with $r_U = r_{mo}\gamma_U$ for the radius observed in the inertial system of the Universe (U) it is yielded:

$$r_U^2 = r_{mo}^2 + \left(\frac{4}{\pi^2} r_S(M)\right)^2, \quad (49)$$

which compares to Eq. (41) gained for the SRT solution but shows again a factor due differing length scales. With the GRT approach, from the perspective of an inertial system in the Universe (U) far away from the mass objects (m, M) the minimum radius that can be observed for the mass object falling is $\approx 0.405r_S$. This compares to the SRT solution derived in the

subsection above yielding a value of r_S .

According to Eq. (41) and Eq. (48), also in the relativistic case in the inertial system of the mass object (mo) it is: $r_{mo} \cong n\lambda_C$. Hence, like in the non-relativistic case given in Eq. (22) for the quantum number, e.g. for a Planck-mass at the boarder of the Universe, we can calculate while setting $r_{gB} := R_U$:

$$n_{GrmaxPl} = \frac{R_U m_{Pl} c_0}{\hbar} = \frac{R_U}{\lambda_C(m_{Pl})}. \quad (50)$$

Consequently, for a higher number of smaller identical mass objects, there must be a limit, due to degenerative pressure. Otherwise, the mass objects would have to occupy even higher energy states also in the gravitational hyperbolic continuum outside of the Universe – like what is known from the Chandrasekhar limit for white dwarf stars [20] - but which would not make sense since contradicting the assumed size R_U of a closed Universe. In contrary, for identical larger mass objects the available quantum states will only be merely filled-up. In the relativistic case the Fermi energy adding on top of the zero-point energy level is based on the relativistic momentum and the de Broglie wavelength, with N the number of states required for identical mass objects:

$$W_{Fr}(R) = \hbar\pi c_0 \left(\frac{3N}{(4/3)\pi^2 R^3}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} = W_{Gh}(R) \left(\frac{9\pi}{4}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}. \quad (51)$$

From Eq. (21), also a minimum for the mass required for an object to exist in the current Universe can be interpreted:

$$m_{minU} = \frac{\hbar}{R_U c_0} = \frac{W_{GhU}}{c_0^2} = 8.031 \cdot 10^{-70} kg. \quad (52)$$

Obviously, thus the Planck mass considering Eq. (9) is the geometric mean of the smallest and the largest possible mass values found in the Universe:

$$m_{Pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c_0}{G}} = \sqrt{m_{minU} M_U} \quad (53)$$

Finally, a minimum for the size of the Universe from current perspective could be hypothesized, if ground state $n_{Gr} = 1$ with ghotons acting between two halves of the mass value of the current Universe is assumed¹¹:

$$R_{U00} = \frac{\hbar}{4M_U c_0} = \frac{\lambda_C(M_U)}{4} = 1.491 \cdot 10^{-97} m. \quad (54)$$

To conclude, the SRT and GRT both provide solutions for an observer in the inertial system of the Universe (U) far away from the interacting mass objects that exhibit a minimum radius for a mass object m attracted by mass object M perceived based on the Schwarzschild radius of mass object M . For large

¹¹ If at minimum size the Universe is determined by degeneration in quantum statistics of mass objects this becomes invalid.

quantum numbers the SRT and GRT solutions do converge towards the non-relativistic solution, as to be expected. Furthermore, both solutions also show the same Taylor approximations, only with SRT and GRT differing only by a one-dimensional distance- versus spherical-length- scale factor.

The minimum radius, i.e. distance between the mass object m and M in both inertial systems – (U) and (mo) is realized for the quantum ground-state $n = 1$.

In (U) it is equivalent to the de Broglie wavelength of mass object m based on relativistic momentum, while the radius will always remain finite, i.e. without singularity – see Eq. (26) and Eq. (41).

In (mo) it is converging towards the reduced Compton wavelength for relativistic velocities. Thus, in the wave-picture such mass object to exist requires this minimum spatial extend. Following this thought for mass objects falling into a black hole, compactification and increase of gravitational tidal forces will lead to their disintegration into fundamental particles, which then will limit further compactification by their respective reduced Compton wavelengths as minimum spatial extends required. In consequence, quantum statistics of identical fundamental particles lead to degeneracy pressure stopping further compactification, as for example in a neutron star [20].

Due to this quantization and spatial minimum extend required for particles, the corresponding kinetic energy assumes finite values as well, i.e. the consideration of quantum mechanical effects in relativistic gravitation results into the avoidance of singularities.

The minimum spatial extend limitation for compactification of mass objects can be interpreted as rooted in the vacuum fluctuations and definition of what a mass object is as such expressed by the quantum mechanical uncertainty – see the Penrose “zigzag picture” of mass in [6].

In the classical SRT and GRT including its respective Schwarzschild solution point-like mass objects and no quantum mechanical effects are considered. Hence, infinite energies may be calculated due to possible distances $r \rightarrow 0$. It is an insight from the EQGM, that classical Newton, SRT and GRT prediction of gravitational collapse by ever compacting mass objects, like what also was the central paradox in electrodynamics in the instable Rutherford atom model, is not to happen if applying a quantum mechanical approach based on the Bohr atom model to these relativistic theories – also see page 1197 in [32].

2. Homogeneous mass density constellations

i) Special relativity approach

A SRT approach shall be given for the potential of a homogenous mass distribution Universe from an inside perspective, i.e. assuming that mass objects were originating from within the Universe.

With the relativistic Bohr model from Eq. (26) for the balance of gravitational and centrifugal force of the mass object in the inertial system of the Universe (U) with considering Eq. (13) it is:

$$F_g = \frac{m_0 \gamma M_U G r_U}{R_U^3} \equiv \frac{m_0 \gamma v^2}{r_U} = F_c. \quad (55)$$

From this with Eq. (9) it is yielded:

$$\gamma_U = \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{n \lambda_C(m)}{R_U}\right)^2} \quad (56)$$

Considering that the maximum possible radius for a mass object m within the Universe is the radius of the Universe as such, also here a maximum quantum number as already given by Eq. (22) can be concluded:

$$n_{maxU}(m) = \frac{R_U}{\lambda_C(m)}, \quad (57)$$

and with this it is $\gamma_{Umax} = \sqrt{2}$.

For the kinetic energy with Eq. (56) it is:

$$W_{krU} = m_0 c_0^2 \left(\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{n \lambda_C(m)}{R_U}\right)^2} - 1 \right), \quad (58)$$

and with this it is $\frac{W_{krUmax}}{W_0(m_0)} = \sqrt{2} - 1 \cong 0.414$. Note that this compares to the value of 0.5 as assumed in the simplified non-relativistic potential shown in Fig. 1. For the kinetic energy term in Eq. (58), a good approximation for the non-relativistic regime $\gamma < 0.25$ is yielded with:

$$W_{krUin} \cong \frac{n^2 W_{GhU}^2}{2W_0(m_0)} \quad (59)$$

Hence, for a mass object that would have fallen into the Universe from “outside” starting from an infinite radius, in the simple classical approach shown in Fig. 1 and based on Eq. (10) with the minimum kinetic energy equal to the mass objects rest energy will appear on-top to the kinetic energy gained within the Universe it is:

$$W_{krU} \cong \frac{3}{2} W_0(m_0) - \frac{n^2 W_{GhU}^2}{2W_0(m_0)}. \quad (60)$$

Again, this is a simplified static approach to capture basic properties of quantized gravitation, not considering the Hubble expansion of the Universe and

propagation of the gravitational effect as limited by the speed of light.

ii) *General relativity approach*

To adopt relativistic effects and the speed of light propagation of gravitational effects for the simplified, static model of the Universe, a General Relativity Theory (GRT) approach shall be made. Starting again from Eq. (42) above for a given point-like mass M , the mass included within a radius in the Universe depends on the actual radius and the mass density of the Universe. However, time to fall in the gravitational field of a distributed versus a point mass M is by factor $\sqrt{2}$ longer – refer again to page 663 in [32]:

$$\tau(r_{mo}, M) = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{r_{mo}}{c_0} \left(\frac{r_{mo}}{r_S(r_{mo}, M)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}},$$

with: $r_S(r_{mo}, M) = \frac{2(\frac{4}{3}\pi r_{mo}^3 \rho_U)G}{c_0^2}$ and:

$$\rho_U = \frac{M_U}{\frac{4}{3}\pi R_U^3}. \quad (61)$$

With this and using Eq. (9) it is yielded:

$$\tau = \frac{\pi R_U}{2 c_0}. \quad (62)$$

This is a remarkable result, as any mass object falling from any radius position in the static Universe would take the same time to approach radius zero. The time is the age of the Universe, including consideration of space beyond the Hubble radius, and multiplied by $\pi/2$ as length scale in GRT is defined on a sphere rather than on a distance. This provides a picture of a reverse big bang, meaning a big crunch converging all mass objects contained in the Universe towards radius zero at the same point in time. This also would imply convergence of the inertial systems (mo) and (U).

Out of Eq. (62) a velocity and kinetic energy of a mass object related to the length-contracted radius r_{mo} can be calculated:

$$v(r_{mo}) = \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{r_{mo}}{R_U} c_0, \text{ and:} \quad (63)$$

With $r_{mo} = \frac{\hbar n}{m_0 v}$ from Eq. (19) it does result:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{\hbar n}{R_U m_0 c_0}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2 n W_{GhU}}{\pi W_0(m_0)}}} \quad (64)$$

This yields $\gamma \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2}{\pi}}} \cong 1.659$ at the boarder of the Universe at R_U for the maximum quantum number

n_{maxU} , still including the spherical length factor $\frac{2}{\pi}$ from GRT. If the length factor would be replaced by the factor one in the radicand, the Lorentz factor would strive towards infinity, rightfully indicating that the mass object may never leave the Universe. If the length factor would be applied as factor to Eq. (64) again, it will become almost similar with the SRT solution as given in Eq. (58).

Developing Eq. (64) into a Taylor-series around the non-relativistic regime $\gamma \rightarrow 1$ with only the first two terms considered, it is yielded:

$$\gamma = 1 + \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{W_{GhU}}{W_0(m_0)} (n - 1), \text{ which delivers for the relativistic kinetic energy for } n \gg 1:$$

$$W_{knr} = m_0 c_0^2 (\gamma - 1) \cong \frac{1}{\pi} n W_{GhU}. \quad (65)$$

This must be compared to the SRT solution in Eq. (59), except for the factor $\frac{1}{\pi}$ due to spherical length scale in GRT versus SRT.

To summarize, the kinetic gravitational energy of a mass object in the homogenous Universe is quantized with a multiple of the universal ghton energy. This indicates that the gravitational energy for a mass object in the Universe stems from a ghton quanta bath contained in the Universe.

The models for the Universe given above are simplified static considerations to shed some light on the gravitational quantization properties: In this the ghton of the Universe as the fundamental gravitational energy quantum W_{GhU} , and $n_{Grmax}(m)$ as the maximum number of quantum states fitting into the Universe for a given mass object are found.

3. *Quantum gravitational coupling*

(a) *Coulombian coupling constant*

To describe the coupling between an object in a gravitation potential and its quantum particles, the gravitational coupling can be derived analogous to the Sommerfeld fine-structure constant for electrodynamics [46].

The Sommerfeld fine-structure constant¹² α_C is based on the Bohr atom model. It relates the velocity of the electron on its trajectory in a hydrogen atom, around the proton at the core, in ground state $n = 1$ to the speed of light. Hence it serves for example to describe emission- and absorption rates of photons from the electron. With the Bohr radius from Eq. (15) the

¹² With subscript C used here to denote that respective coupling constant is related to the Coulomb potential.

electron velocity is: $v_{eB} = \frac{h}{2\pi r_B m_e} = \frac{q^2}{2\varepsilon_0 h}$, and hence:

$$\alpha_C = \frac{v_{eB}}{c_0} = \frac{q^2}{4\pi\varepsilon_0 h c_0} = 7.292 \cdot 10^{-3}. \quad (66)$$

This is based on a classical Bohr model that is only valid since the value of α is much smaller than one, i.e. $v_{eB} \ll c_0$. If a coupling parameter for heavier atoms with multiple elementary charges from the atomic nucleus acting on a shell electron should be defined, a relativistic calculation is required, as described in section II.C.1 above.

Accordingly, a general coupling parameter observed in the inertial system of the Universe (U) based on the Lorentz factor along with $\alpha_{xU} = \frac{v_x}{c_0}$ that can thus never exceed the value of one is defined as:

$$\alpha_{xU} = \frac{v_{xU}}{c_0} = \sqrt{1 - \gamma_{xU}^{-2}}. \quad (67)$$

(b) Gravitational coupling constant

In direct analogy to the Coulomb potential term contained in Eq. (66) and with Eq. (50), for the electron and proton a gravitational coupling constant for the ground state at $n = 1$ can be defined for the non-relativistic case based on the Eq. (67) as:

$$\alpha_{GepU} = \frac{v_{me}}{c_0} = \frac{m_e m_p G}{h c_0} = 3.217 \cdot 10^{-42} \quad (68)$$

(c) Generalized gravitational coupling parameter

To generalize, for elementary particles contained in the standard model of particle physics for a particle mass m_x in the gravitational potential of another particle mass m_y , a gravitational coupling parameter considering Eq. (9) can be written as:

$$\alpha_{Gxy} = \frac{v_{m_x}}{c_0} = \frac{m_x m_y G}{h c_0} = n_{Gmax}(m_x) \frac{m_y}{M_U} \quad (69)$$

Since all elementary particles have a mass much less than the Planck mass the resulting gravitational coupling factors will always be in the non-relativistic regime, thus assume values by far less than one:

$$\alpha_{Gxy} = \frac{m_x m_y}{m_{Pl}^2} = \frac{m_x m_y}{m_{minU} M_U} = \frac{R_U}{\lambda_C(m_x) M_U} \ll 1, \quad (70)$$

while having used Eq. (53) and $\lambda_C(m_{minU}) = R_U$.

The kinetic energy out of the gravitational interaction

¹³ Here the straight fall converting gravitational potential energy to kinetic energy is assumed: $W_{kin} = -W_{pot}$. Recall that in case of mass object m being on a circular track around the gravitational potential of mass object M due to the Virial theorem for the non-relativistic case based on the balance of gravitational and centripetal forces according to $F_g = \frac{mMG}{r^2} \equiv \frac{mvU^2}{r} = F_c$ it is:

$$W_{kin} = -\frac{1}{2} W_{pot}.$$

with Eq. [19] and Eq. [68] can be expressed as¹³:

$$W_{gkxy}(r) = (\gamma - 1) m_{x0} c_0^2 = \alpha_{Gxy} W_{Gh}(r). \quad (71)$$

This can be used to describe the special case of the gravitational self-coupling as well, if setting $r_{xs} \equiv \lambda_C(m_{x0})$ in the inertial system of the mass object (mo), delivering:

$$\alpha_{Gxsmo} = \gamma - 1. \quad (72)$$

Hence, in the inertial system of the mass object (mo) the coupling parameter may exceed the value of one. This means that the gravitational self-coupling energy of a mass is its rest energy and vice versa and can be understood with the Penrose picture of mass [6]. Note that Eq. (71) and (72) are valid also for coupling parameters describing other fundamental forces.

Obviously, the coupling parameter changes in case of further energies imposed to the mass object, so that for a mass object moving at ultra-relativistic velocity it is:

$$\alpha = \frac{v}{c_0} \rightarrow 1, \text{ and thus the kinetic gravitational energy}$$

of a mass object becomes identical to the ghton energy based on the distance between the attracting mass objects. Conclusively, for any mass interacting with the Universe always a relativistic consideration according to Eq. (67) is needed, and Eq. (71) cannot be applied to calculate the coupling. This means with considerations out of section II.A. that any mass in the Universe must be considered as being inside a black hole. Assuming a parabolic potential in the Universe as described in section II.C.2, at gravitational zero-point level $r = R_U$ with $W_{zp} = W_{kin} = (\gamma - 1) m c_0^2$ and $\gamma = 2$ results to $v_U = \sqrt{3}/2 c_0$, hence the minimum gravitational coupling parameter for a mass object in the Universe assumes:

$$\alpha_{Gzp} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} = 0.866. \quad (73)$$

Within the Universe α_{mMUG} will be running, i.e., increase further towards up to the value of one, if mass objects approach speed of light. Hence strong emission- and absorption interaction of ghotons with mass objects in the Universe can be expected.

4. Quantum state occupancy and particles in the Universe

In this subsection the quantum state statistics for elementary particles as gravitational many-body

systems in the Universe shall be set up.

As already described in section II.B.3, in the spherical Bohr atom model the number of available states for a single electron as a fundamental particle is given by Eq. (23) with $N_{as} = g_s n^3$, while $g_s = 2$ is the spin degeneracy factor.

In the Universe many-body systems for each fundamental particle¹⁴ must be considered, while each of these can be seen in their inertial system as being located at $r = 0$, since the Universe has no center. Accordingly, each particle does generate a gravitational potential well to all other particles. For N_x particles of the same kind this means the number of required states is:

$$N_{rs} = N_x^2. \quad (74)$$

This includes the self-coupling in the case of $N_x = 1$, where one state is required.

In case N_{rs} becomes larger than the number of available states N_{as} for the respective fundamental particle, additional “excess” energy states will be required to still fit all particles into the space of the Universe. An excess occupancy factor can be defined as:

$$\zeta_{es} = \frac{N_{rs}}{N_{as}} \quad (75)$$

In the relativistic view these excess states will result in differentiation of the relativistic mass from the particles in the already occupied available states in the space of the Universe to not violate the required fermion quantum statistics.

5. Particle system immanent quantum interaction

In this subsection quantum mechanical systems of free mass objects shall be analyzed along the Klein-Gordon Equation (KGE) and the Schrödinger Equation (SE). The questions to be answered are, what kind of quantum potential functions V_{qp} , kinetic energies and quantum statistic properties are immanent to such systems.

(a) Two-particle system in one dimension

The KGE [6] is set up in the simplest, one-dimensional form, with one equation for each of two free mass objects 1 and 2 governed by a joint wavefunction:

$$\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi_{12} = \left[\Delta_{1/2} - \frac{m_{01/2}^2 c_0^2}{\hbar^2} + \frac{V_{qp1/2}^2}{\hbar^2 c_0^2} \right] \Psi_{12}, \quad (76)$$

with the Laplace operator in the one-dimensional case as: $\Delta_{1/2} = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r_{1/2}^2}$.

For the two free, distinct mass objects, the joint wavefunction is defined as a product of the wavefunctions of each mass object, with their location vectors \vec{r}_1 and \vec{r}_2 , respectively – see page 597 in [6]:

$$\Psi_{12}(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, t) = \Psi_1(\vec{r}_1, t) \Psi_2(\vec{r}_2, t), \quad (77)$$

However, for the same kind of two fermions (–) or same kind of two bosons (+) it is:

$$\Psi_{12}(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, t) = \Psi_1(\vec{r}_1, t) \Psi_2(\vec{r}_2, t) \mp \Psi_1(\vec{r}_2, t) \Psi_2(\vec{r}_1, t). \quad (77a)$$

The wavefunction for each mass object is defined by an Eq. (78) as:

$$\Psi_{1/2}(\vec{r}, t) = A_{1/2} \exp [i(\omega_{1/2} t + \vec{k}_{1/2} \vec{r}) + \varphi_{01/2}],$$

with: $\omega_{1/2} = \vec{c}_0 \vec{k}_{1/2} = \frac{W_{1/2}}{\hbar}$, and: $\vec{k}_{1/2} = \frac{\vec{p}_{1/2}}{\hbar}$ while $\varphi_{01/2}$ is an arbitrary phase angle.

First, we do continue with the case of distinct mass objects. Hence the joint wavefunction writes as:

$$\Psi_{12} = A_{12} \exp [i\varphi_{12}], \quad \text{with:} \quad (79)$$

$\varphi_{12} = ((\omega_1 + \omega_2)t - \vec{k}_1 \vec{r}_1 - \vec{k}_2 \vec{r}_2) + \varphi_0$, that can be rewritten into:

$$\varphi_{12} = \frac{1}{\hbar} [\hbar(\omega_1 + \omega_2)t - (\vec{p}_1 \vec{r}_1 + \vec{p}_2 \vec{r}_2)] + \varphi_0 \quad (80)$$

As can be seen this allows for a separation approach: $\Psi_{1/2}(\vec{r}_{1/2}, t) = \Psi_{1/2}(\vec{r}_{1/2}) \Psi_{1/2}(t)$ with the time-dependent part as: $\Psi_{1/2}(t) = \exp[i(\omega_1 + \omega_2)t]$ exhibiting the absolute value of one, regardless of time.

The absolute value of the joint wavefunction squared delivers the probability density for the mass objects, while this must be unity integrated over the one-dimensional spatial extension, i.e. the confinement radii of the particles, which is at maximum given by the size of the Universe:

$$\int_0^{RU} \int_0^{RU} |\Psi_{12}(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, t)|^2 d r_1 d r_2 \equiv 1, \quad (81)$$

resulting into: $A_{12} = \frac{1}{RU^2}$ for the one-dimensional case considered here.

Now out of rearranging the KGE, the quantum potential function shall be determined as:

¹⁴ Here the term „fundamental“ means a fermionic particle that to current knowledge is not composed of further particles, i.e. as leptons and quarks, and shall not be confused with composed particles like e.g. the neutron or proton.

$$\frac{V_{qp1/2}^2 - m_{01/2}^2 c_0^4}{\hbar^2 c_0^2} = \frac{1}{\Psi_{12}} \left[\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \Psi_{12} - \Delta_{1/2} \Psi_{12} \right] \quad (82)$$

I want to analyze this for a static, i.e. time-independent potential, thus a further simplification can be made by only considering the time-independent solution of the KGE, so that $\Psi_{1/2}(\vec{r}_{1/2}, t) \rightarrow \Psi_{1/2}(\vec{r}_{1/2})$. Therefore, also the time derivatives for the wavefunction are no longer considered, while the potential function is assumed to be time-independent in Eq. (82). Thus, it is:

$$\frac{V_{qp1/2}^2 - m_{01/2}^2 c_0^4}{\hbar^2 c_0^2} = \frac{-1}{\Psi_{12}} [\Delta_{1/2} \Psi_{12}]. \quad (83)$$

Inserting the wavefunction yields for the right-hand side of Eq. (83):

$$\begin{aligned} & -A_{12} \exp[i\varphi_{12}] \left(-\left(\frac{\partial \varphi_{12}}{\partial r_{1/2}}\right)^2 + i \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_{12}}{\partial r_{1/2}^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{A_{12} \exp[i\varphi_{12}]}{A_{12} \exp[i\varphi_{12}]} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial \varphi_{12}}{\partial r_{1/2}}\right)^2 - i \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_{12}}{\partial r_{1/2}^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

Since the left-hand side of the Eq. (83) containing the quantum potential and the rest energy of the mass objects must not have an imaginary part, it is required that:

$\frac{\partial^2 \varphi_{12}}{\partial r_{1/2}^2} \equiv 0$, and consecutively by integrating:

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_{12}}{\partial r_{1/2}} \equiv c_1 \neq f(r_{1/2}), \text{ with: } c_1 \in \mathbb{R} \quad (85)$$

Now I apply Eq. (80), the derivation after $r_{1/2}$, the momentum conservation, and a setting w.l.o.g. as $\vec{r}_1 = \vec{r} = -\vec{r}_2$, i.e. the effective distance between the particles being $2r$. Accordingly like with the signs of the coordinates, it is set: $\vec{p}_1 = \vec{p} = -\vec{p}_2$. With this we get a differential equation as condition:

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_{12}}{\partial r_{1/2}} = c_1 = \frac{-2}{\hbar} \left[\frac{\partial \vec{p}}{\partial r} \vec{r} + \vec{p} \right], \quad (86)$$

While for the wave phase function out of Eq. (80) it is:

$$\varphi_{12} = -\frac{2\vec{p}\vec{r}}{\hbar} + \varphi_0 \quad (87)$$

As can be easily seen the generic solution function for Eq. (86) is:

$$\vec{p}(r) = \frac{c_2}{r} - \frac{\hbar}{2} c_1, \text{ with: } c_1, c_2 \in \mathbb{R} \quad (88)$$

Furthermore, based on Eq. (87) and integrating

Eq. (86) the wave phase function must comply to:

$$\varphi_{12} \equiv c_1 r + c_3 = -\frac{2\vec{p}\vec{r}}{\hbar} + \varphi_0, \text{ with } c_3 \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (89)$$

The simple case would implicate that $c_1 = -\frac{2\vec{p}}{\hbar}$, i.e. the momentum be a constant, or even as a trivial case being zero.

However, the non-trivial case is found for looking at Eq. (86) with $\frac{\partial \varphi_{12}}{\partial r_{1/2}} = c_1 = 0$, i.e. the phase of the wavefunction being at an extremum or saddle point¹⁵, while this results to:

$$\vec{p}(\vec{r}) = \frac{(\varphi_0 - c_3)\hbar}{\vec{r}}, \text{ and thus: } c_2 = (\varphi_0 - c_3). \quad (90)$$

The kinetic energy for the mass object can be calculated from the relativistic energy-momentum relation [44] as:

$$W_{kin1/2} = \sqrt{[m_{01/2} c_0^2]^2 + [|\vec{p}(\vec{r})| c_0]^2} - m_{01/2} c_0^2.$$

Hence and w. l. o. g. setting $\varphi_0 = 0$:

$$W_{kin1/2} = \sqrt{W_{01/2}^2 + [c_2 W_{Gh}(r)]^2} - W_{01/2}. \quad (91)$$

In this with Eq. (71) the constant c_2 can be identified as a coupling parameter $0 < \alpha_x < 1$ between the ghton energy of the two-particle system confinement¹⁶ and the kinetic energy for the mass objects out of this quantum interaction.

With this the joint wavefunction of the two mass objects assumes a fixed complex value:

$$\Psi_{12} = \frac{1}{R_U^2} \exp[-i\alpha_x]. \quad (92)$$

Note that if knowing that the two particles are confined within the distance $2r$ by the quantum interaction described above, in Eq. (81) and Eq. (92) R_U needs to be replaced by $2r$.

Feeding these results into Eq. (84) does yield for the quantum potential function of the KGE:

$$V_{qp1/2KGE} = m_{01/2} c_0^2 \quad (93)$$

For the sake of completeness, I want to show the same approach while using the SE instead of the KGE:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Psi_{12} = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_{1/2}} \Delta_{1/2} + V_{pot1/2} \right] \Psi_{12} \quad (94)$$

The derivation is similar and yields the same result for

¹⁵ As it is: $\frac{\partial \varphi_{12}}{\partial r_{1/2}} \hbar = \frac{\partial S}{\partial r_{1/2}} = 0$ this complies to the mandatory principle of stationary action first introduced by J.-L. Lagrange and W. R. Hamilton – see for example [6].

¹⁶ As will be shown in section III.L below, the ghton energy is also the gravitational vacuum energy for a mass object.

the momentum function $\vec{p}(r)$ as in Eq. (88), while the quantum potential results to:

$$V_{qp1/2} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_{1/2}} \left(\frac{\partial \phi_{12}}{\partial r_{1/2}} \right)^2 = 0 \quad (95)$$

This means, although there is no explicit potential taking effect on the system of the two mass objects - apart from the rest energy in the KGE context - the two particles do exhibit an interaction with $p \sim \frac{\hbar}{r}$ and $W_{kin} \sim \frac{\hbar}{r}$ as can be seen from their “self-immanent” momentum and kinetic energy derived here out of the KGE and SE.

To complete the analysis, I want to address the case with the two mass objects being same of the kind fermions.

As it was set $\vec{r}_1 = \vec{r} = -\vec{r}_2$, Eq. (77a) for same of the kind fermions would lead to $\Psi_{12}(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, t) = \Psi_a(\vec{r}, t)\Psi_a(-\vec{r}, t) - \Psi_a(-\vec{r}, t)\Psi_a(\vec{r}, t) = 0$ due to the Pauli principle as two fermions cannot be in the same quantum state (a). However, for different quantum states (a and b) assumed, it is: $\Psi_{12F}(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, t) = \Psi_a(\vec{r}, t)\Psi_b(-\vec{r}, t) - \Psi_a(-\vec{r}, t)\Psi_b(\vec{r}, t) = A_x^2 \left[\exp\left[\frac{-i}{\hbar}(2\vec{p}\vec{r})\right] - \exp\left[\frac{-i}{\hbar}(-2\vec{p}\vec{r})\right] \right] = A_x^2 \left[-2\sin\left[\frac{-i}{\hbar}(2\vec{p}\vec{r})\right] \right]$. Thus, this results to the same phase angle of the wavefunction – and hence the same consecutive results - like for distinct mass objects derived with Eq. (87):

$$\phi_{12} = -\frac{2\vec{p}\vec{r}}{\hbar} + \phi_0$$

Also for Bosons that may assume same quantum states, that same phase angle and results can be concluded: $\Psi_{12B}(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, t) = \Psi(\vec{r}, t)\Psi(-\vec{r}, t) + \Psi(-\vec{r}, t)\Psi(\vec{r}, t) = 2A_x^2 \exp\left[\frac{-i}{\hbar}(2\vec{p}\vec{r})\right]$.

Thus, for different mass objects, as well as for identical fermions and identical bosons, for the momentum out of Eq. (90) three cases may arise depending on the parameter c_2 being zero (neutrality, no interaction), or negative (attraction of objects due to antiparallel location and negatively signed anti-parallel momentum vectors), or positive (repulsion between objects due to antiparallel location and positively signed anti-parallel momentum vectors).

In other words: A gravitational- or Coulomb-type of interaction between mass objects is immanent as a quantum mechanical entanglement effect captured by the joined wavefunction as such in the KGE and SE, thus given by the sheer existence of the two mass objects in the Universe. In this the principle of stationary action applied above plays a key role.

(b) Two-particle system in three dimensions

To reflect reality of the Universe, the KGE and SE shall now be solved for the three-dimensional spherical coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) and respective components used for the momentum and the location vectors of the free two objects. W.l.o.g. and again considering conservation of momentum with the sum of both momentums being zero, I do define:

$$\vec{r}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} r_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \vec{r}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} r_2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \vec{p}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} p_{r1} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \vec{p}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} p_{r2} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

with: $r_1 = 0, r_2 = r$, and: $p_{r1} = -p_r = -p_{r2}$.

The three-dimensional spherical Laplace operator is defined as:

$$\Delta = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cot(\theta)}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2}.$$

Again, the absolute value of the joint wavefunction squared delivers the probability density for the mass objects, while this must be unity integrated over the confinement volumes of the particles, in the Universe:

$$\int_0^{V_U} \int_0^{V_U} |\Psi_{12}(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, t)|^2 dV_1 dV_2 \equiv 1, \quad (96)$$

resulting into: $A_{12} = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{4}{3}\pi R_U^3\right)^2}$ for the three-

dimensional case considered. Also, here, if knowing that the two objects are confined within the distance e.g. r by the quantum interaction described above, in Eq. (96) R_U needs to be replaced by this distance.

Taking the same approach for the KGE with the wavefunction and its derivatives contained as with Eq. (83), reformulated into Eq. (84) and the phase function contained in the wave function from Eq. (87) for the one-dimensional case yields a condition, since the imaginary part of the potential function must be zero. An Eq. (97) is defined as:

$$\text{Im} \left\{ \frac{\Delta \Psi_{12}}{\Psi_{12}} \right\} = \frac{1}{\hbar} \left[\left(2 \frac{\partial p_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 p_r}{\partial r^2} r \right) + \left(\frac{2}{r} \left(p_r + \frac{\partial p_r}{\partial r} r \right) \right) + \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 p_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} \theta \right) + \left(\frac{\cot(\theta)}{r^2} \frac{\partial p_\theta}{\partial \theta} \theta \right) + \left(\frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 p_\phi}{\partial \phi^2} \phi \right) \right] \equiv 0.$$

Based on the initial setting above with the angular components for the location and momentum vectors being zero, now w.l.o.g. it is concluded that also the angular derivatives are zero. Thus, any interaction between the objects is only to happen along the radial dimension. The remaining terms out of Eq. (97) do provide a differential equation for the momentum:

$$p_r(r) = -\frac{r^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2 p_r}{\partial r^2} - 2r \frac{\partial p_r}{\partial r}. \quad (98)$$

For this, the generic solution is:

$$p_r(r) = \frac{c_1'}{r^2} + \frac{c_2'}{r}, \text{ with: } c_1', c_2' \in \mathbb{R} \quad (99)$$

Feeding this into the expression for the potential function from the KGE according to Eq. (83) yields:

$$V_{qp1/2} = \sqrt{m_{01/2}^2 c_0^4 + \hbar^2 c_0^2 \frac{\Delta\Psi_{12}}{\Psi_{12}}}. \quad (100)$$

However, as seen from the one-dimensional KGE solution above, the potential function exhibits only the rest energy of the respective particle. Hence not only the imaginary part of $\frac{\Delta\Psi_{12}}{\Psi_{12}}$ must be zero as considered above, but also the real part:

$$Re \left\{ \frac{\Delta\Psi_{12}}{\Psi_{12}} \right\} = \frac{-1}{\hbar^2} \left(p_r + \frac{\partial p_r}{\partial r} r \right)^2 = \frac{-1}{\hbar^2} \left(\frac{-c_1'}{r^2} \right)^2 \equiv 0$$

Accordingly, c_1' must be zero – or only have an imaginary part, which is not followed up here. Hence this yields the same hyperbolic result for the three-dimensional as for the one-dimensional treatment:

$$p_r(r) = \frac{c_2'}{r}, \text{ with: } c_2' \in \mathbb{R} \quad (101)$$

(c) *Identical many-particle system in one dimension*

I now extend the analysis of the two-particle to a many-particle system of identical particles in one dimension with mass m each.

The joint wavefunction for the system of N particles is given again as the product of the wavefunctions of the particles:

$$\Psi_N(\vec{r}_0, \dots, \vec{r}_{N-1}, t) = \prod_{j=0}^{N-1} \Psi_j(\vec{r}_j, t), \quad (102)$$

with the wavefunction per particle as defined already in the section above:

$$\Psi_j = A_j \exp[i\varphi_j], \text{ and:} \quad (103)$$

$$\varphi_j = (\omega_j t - \vec{k}_j \vec{r}_j) + \varphi_{0j} \quad (104)$$

As for the two-particle approach derived above, for the time-independent case the resulting joint wavefunction is:

$$\Psi_N = A_N \exp[i\varphi_N], \text{ with:} \quad (105)$$

$$\varphi_N = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \varphi_j = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \frac{-\vec{p}_j \vec{r}_j}{\hbar}. \quad (106)$$

Building on the two-particle approach the N identical particles are arranged half in the negative and positive range around the origin of the one-dimensional space and are equidistantly separated by a distance r_N . On the positive axis it is: $\vec{r}_j = j\vec{r}_N + \vec{r}_N/2$, while on the

negative axis this term is used with a negative sign. The direction of the momentums of the particles is set towards the origin, so that their vector sum is zero and thus fulfills the conservation of momentum. Moreover, since particles are identical, and each particle must be considered to reside in the center of the Universe, their absolute momentums must be identical as well: $|\vec{p}_j| = |\vec{p}_N|$. Note that with this setup to realize the required wavefunction as in Eq. (106) a factor of two must be introduced to the terms describing the particles on both parts of the axis. With this and N as an even number I define Eq. (107) as:

$$\varphi_N = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \frac{\vec{p}_j \vec{r}_j}{-\hbar} = 2 \left[\sum_{j=0}^{\left(\frac{N}{2}-1\right)} \frac{-\vec{p}_j(-\vec{r}_j)}{-\hbar} + \sum_{j=0}^{\left(\frac{N}{2}-1\right)} \frac{\vec{p}_j \vec{r}_j}{-\hbar} \right],$$

Delivering while inserting the parameters as above:

$$\varphi_N = \left(\frac{N^2}{2} \right) \left(\frac{\vec{p}_N \vec{r}_N}{-\hbar} \right) = c_{3N} = -\widehat{\alpha}_{xN}. \quad (108)$$

This contains the case for $N = 2$ already described in Eq. (89) and Eq. (90) above as:

$$\varphi_{N=2} = \varphi_{12} = \left(\frac{-2\vec{p}_N \vec{r}_N}{\hbar} \right) = c_3 = -\alpha_x \quad (109)$$

While the phase function in Eq. (108) is fixed at a parameter as shown in Eq. (89) and with considering Eq. (90) this translates into an overall coupling parameter $\widehat{\alpha}_{xN}$. Eq. (108) shows that between N particles $\left(\frac{N^2}{2} \right)$ coupling relations do exist. To obtain the total coupling taking effect per particle and hence causing its kinetic interaction energy a normalization¹⁷ by $\left(\frac{N}{2} \right)$ is required, yielding:

$$\alpha_{xN} = \frac{\widehat{\alpha}_{xN}}{\left(\frac{N}{2} \right)} = N\alpha_x. \quad (110)$$

This means, the coupling parameter in a population of N identical particles is by the factor N stronger than between two identical particles.

Now I reconsider from section II.C.3, that in the three-dimensional spherical space, each energy state for fermions along the radial quantum number and with the maximum number of differing energy states available as defined in Eq. (50) is: $n_{GrR} = n_{Grmax}(m) = \frac{R U m c_0}{\hbar}$. These energy states are additionally degenerated along the two angular quantum numbers $n_{Gr\phi}$, $n_{Gr\theta}$, and the spin degeneracy $g_s = 2$ according to the Pauli principle. Thus, the degeneration at a given energy level adds at maximum $2n^2$ states, hence resulting to a total number of available states of: $n_{as} = 2n^3$, with $n =$

¹⁷ Considering the value two in the divisor of $\left(\frac{N}{2} \right)$ reflects that one coupling relation is defined between two particles.

$n_{Grmax}(m)$.

However, in the one-dimensional case if all energy states are occupied as $N = g_s n_{Grmax}(m)$ we yield with Eq. (110):

$$\alpha_{xN} = 2 \frac{R_{Um} c_0}{h} \alpha_x \quad (111)$$

For the three-dimensional case, in addition to the different energy states along the radial quantum number n_{Gr} the degenerated angular quantum states at the same energy levels could be filled. If the entire particle system would be at a temperature of $T = 0K$, all angular states would be filled first before an additional radial energy state at higher energy would be occupied. However, as shown above the kinetic energy for mass objects in the Universe is at relativistic levels, i.e. high temperatures, since mass objects are found at different radii, and also different angles. Thus, it must be concluded that all radial energy states are occupied, as the number of identical particles N by far exceeds n_{Gr} . Thus, the angular states are partially not occupied, if the number of identical particles N remains below $2(n_{Grmax}(m))^3$.

To conclude, Eq. (111) then will also apply in the three-dimensional Universe.

(d) Systems with many distinct particles

A particle system with a total of N particles containing the same even number distinct particles A and B shall be considered based on Eq. (106):

$$\varphi_{NAB} = 2 \left[\sum_{j=0}^{\left(\frac{N}{2}-1\right)} \frac{-\vec{p}_A(-\vec{r}_j)}{-\hbar} + \sum_{j=0}^{\left(\frac{N}{2}-1\right)} \frac{\vec{p}_B \vec{r}_j}{-\hbar} \right] = \frac{N^2}{4} \left(\frac{\vec{p}_A \vec{r}}{-\hbar} + \frac{\vec{p}_B \vec{r}}{-\hbar} \right) \quad (112)$$

Two interpretations do result. First, with Eq. (108) and Eq. (110) it is:

$$\alpha_{NAB1} = \frac{N}{2} (\alpha_{AA} + \alpha_{BB}), \quad (113)$$

Second, another view is to consider the $N/2$ pairs of particle A and B as:

$$\alpha_{NAB2} = N \alpha_{AB}, \quad (114)$$

Combining and weighting both interpretations same the result for the normalized mixed coupling factor taking effect on a particle AB is,

$$\alpha_{ANB} = \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha_{AA}}{2} + \frac{\alpha_{AB}}{2} + \frac{\alpha_{BA}}{2} + \frac{\alpha_{BB}}{2} \right), \text{ while} \quad (115)$$

due to symmetry, it is $\alpha_{AB} = \alpha_{BA}$.

Thus, for particle A and particle B the coupling per particle is:

$$\alpha_A = \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha_{AA}}{2} + \frac{\alpha_{AB}}{2} \right) \text{ and } \alpha_B = \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha_{BA}}{2} + \frac{\alpha_{BB}}{2} \right) \quad (116)$$

A simple proof for Eq. (115) results from considering identical particles A and B yielding the same result as in Eq. (110).

Hence, obviously the different particles do constitute a joint quantum system which is not just the sum of both particle sets considered separately.

This solution can also be derived by imagining a visualization of the coupling factors α contained in a two-dimensional matrix with $N \times N$ elements per dimension, while the coupling between two concrete particles is given as per matrix element.

For the visualization for a system containing N particles and thereof two particles of type A and $N - 2$ particles of type B the joint wavefunction can be written as:

$$\varphi_{A2B} = \alpha_{AA} + 2 \left(\frac{N}{2} - 1 \right) \alpha_{AB} + \left(\frac{N}{2} - 1 \right)^2 \alpha_{BB}. \quad (117)$$

Hence the normalized mixed coupling factor for both particles in this quantum system is:

$$\alpha_{A2B} = \frac{4}{N} \left[\alpha_{AA} + \left(\frac{N}{2} - 1 \right) \alpha_{AB} + \left(\frac{N}{2} - 1 \right) \alpha_{BA} + \left(\frac{N}{2} - 1 \right)^2 \alpha_{BB} \right] \quad (118)$$

Again, a simple proof for Eq. (118) results from considering identical particles A and B which gives the same result as in Eq. (110).

Out of Eq. (118), for particle A the total coupling per particle is:

$$\alpha_A = \frac{4}{2} \left[\alpha_{AA} + \left(\frac{N}{2} - 1 \right) \alpha_{AB} \right], \text{ meaning} \quad (119)$$

for $N \gg 1$ it is: $\alpha_A \rightarrow N \alpha_{AB}$.

For particle B the total coupling per particle is:

$$\alpha_B = \frac{4}{N-2} \left[\left(\frac{N}{2} - 1 \right) \alpha_{BA} + \left(\frac{N}{2} - 1 \right)^2 \alpha_{BB} \right], \text{ meaning} \quad (120)$$

for $N \gg 1$ it is: $\alpha_B \rightarrow N \alpha_{BB}$.

Also here, the different particles do constitute a joint quantum system, while regardless of the number of particles contained per particle type the strength of total coupling per minority particle A will be proportional to the total number of particles in the system and determined by the coupling towards the dominant majority particle type¹⁸.

¹⁸ This is an important result that will be used to show that leptons and their respective antiparticles will exhibit the same

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since mass objects do mostly differ, in the EQGM this offsets the minimum energy level for each value of mass as can be seen from Eq. (60) for the gravon energy above. Moreover, the Universe appears only homogeneous at scale, but is made of clusters of galaxies, solar systems, stars, planets, dust, gas, etc. as local structures, all of them representing gravitational potential wells.

This leads to coupled potentials of different size. Superposition of quantum states can be assumed to lead to split-up of energy states into quasi-continuums for objects being in proximity, as this is well-known for electrons in the Coulomb potentials within solid-state crystals. Concluding, we can assume that every composed mass object is finding an unoccupied energy state in the current Universe.

However, as shown in the section II.C.5 above this is not valid for same of a kind, like for fundamental and elementary particles, but depending on the number of particles may even require “excess (energy) states” to comply to fermion quantum statistic laws.

Quantization effects in the motion of mass objects may become obvious under some circumstances - as for example with the zero-point acceleration in intergalactic space at the outer range of galaxies - but not be perceived due to tiny ghton energies between gravons and/or continuum effects in most other cases.

Note that the EQGM derived above does not require the existence of a space beyond the radius of the Universe. This is since I have described it also based on a quantum mechanical potential well perspective from within the Universe.

A. Explanation for Dark Matter effect and quantum gravitation law

At a galaxy Newton gravitational acceleration is imposed on any mass object with:

$$g_N(r) = \frac{M_{Gx}G}{r^2}. \quad (121)$$

According to the EQGM described in this work, a gravitational zero-point quantum fluctuation acceleration in the Universe would need to take effect as well.

Looking into the modified Newton dynamics (MOND)

approach, which is empirically fitted to observations [9], the MOND fit models [15] are:

$$g_{MOND}(r) = \frac{M_{Gx}G}{\mu\left(\frac{g_{MOND}(r)}{a_0}\right)r^2} \quad (122)$$

with estimated $a_0 = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ m/s}^2$, while the fit functions are defined as:

$$\mu_1(x) = \frac{x}{1+x}, \quad (123a)$$

$$\text{and alternatively: } \mu_2(x) = \frac{x}{\sqrt{1+x^2}}. \quad (123b)$$

Out of this, it is gained with μ_1 :

$$g_{MOND1}(r) = \frac{M_{Gx}G + \sqrt{M_{Gx}^2G^2 + 4r^2a_0M_{Gx}G}}{2r^2}, \quad (124)$$

while applying μ_2 yields an Eq. (125):

$$g_{MOND2}(r) = \sqrt{\frac{M_{Gx}^2G^2 + \sqrt{M_{Gx}^4G^4 + 4r^4a_0^2M_{Gx}^2G^2}}{2r^4}}.$$

Meaning that for $g_{MOND}(r) \gg a_0$ the gravitational acceleration equals the Newton law, while for $g_{MOND}(r) \ll a_0$, i.e. with large values for r , it behaves like:

$$g_{MOND}(r) \rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{a_0M_{Gx}G}}{r}. \quad (126)$$

In the following I want to gain some insights into the effects behind the MOND using the EQGM.

It was found with Eq. (8) above, that the value for the zero-point gravitational quantum fluctuation acceleration of a mass object in the Universe a_U appears to be identical to the MOND fit parameter a_0 . From this, I can rewrite Eq. (126) so that $g_{MOND}(r) \rightarrow \sqrt{a_U g_N(r)}$ results in the deep-MOND regime, i.e. for large values of r it delivers the geometric mean of the Newtonian acceleration and the zero-point quantum fluctuation acceleration for a mass object in the Universe.

Since both acceleration vectors can be seen as stochastic quantum variables described by variances - see section II - the overall acceleration can be understood as a covariance of quantum uncertainty accelerations: $Cov(\vec{a}_U, \vec{g}_N(r)) = \vec{a}_U \vec{g}_N(r)$. We find a special case here, with covariance simply equaling the product of both stochastic variables. This means the vectors are correlated; hence the scalar product is at its maximum, meaning they do exhibit identical direction for the accelerations¹⁹. This also leads to the

Coulomb force coupling strength even if their total numbers in the Universe are different – see section III.J below.

¹⁹ The covariance for two stochastic variables is defined as: $Cov(X, Y) = \sigma_x\sigma_y = E(XY) - E(X)E(Y)$. Here, with the expectation value $E(a_U) = 0$ due to quantum fluctuation, while only the expectation value for the product of the two stochastic

Heisenberg uncertainty inequation as in Eq. (11) becoming an equation, i.e. following the principle of stationary action / minimum energy required by acceleration uncertainty being the sum of parallel vectors for $\vec{g}_N(r)$ and \vec{a}_U .

To analyze this, I do derive a perturbation approach for a mass object in the internal gravitation field of a galaxy. In this the zero-point quantum fluctuation acceleration in the Universe is acting on the location of the mass object as an on-top external field yielding an Eq. (127) as:

$$\Delta g_{zp}(r) = M_{Gx}G \left[\frac{1}{(r - \Delta r_g)^2} - \frac{1}{(r + \Delta r_g)^2} \right] \cong \frac{4M_{Gx}G a_U}{c_0^2 r},$$

or with using Eq. (8) and Eq. (9):

$$\Delta g_{zp}(r) = \frac{2M_{Gx}c_0^2}{M_U(1-(r/R_U)^2)^2 r} \cong \frac{2M_{Gx}c_0^2}{M_U r}, \quad (128)$$

with the approximations on the right-hand sides being valid, if the distance r is by at least an order of magnitude smaller than the radius of the Universe.

The effective location-induced acceleration perturbation is written as: $\Delta r_g = \frac{1}{4} a_U \tau_g^2 = \frac{r^2}{R_U}$, with the propagation time for the gravitational effect to emerge between the mass center of the galaxy and the mass object: $\tau_g = \frac{2r}{c_0}$. Note that despite the location symmetry of the quantum fluctuation, due to the non-linearity of the Newtonian gravitation this perturbative acceleration is non-zero and directed towards the mass center of the galaxy, i.e. being parallel to the Newtonian vector.

Another conclusive feature in this model is, that a mass object could never leave the Universe, since r approaching R_U would lead to an infinite acceleration holding it back.

Based on the MOND empirical model, the gravitation caused by the external field effect (EFE) [15] in the case that $a_{int} < a_{ext} < a_0 \equiv a_U$ can be calculated from the quantum fluctuation perturbation of the Newtonian setup above including a scale-up factor γ_{EFE} , hence yielding:

$$\Delta g_{zpeFE}(r) = \gamma_{EFE} \Delta g_{zp}(r) = \sqrt{a_U g_N(r)}, \quad \text{since:}$$

$$\gamma_{EFE} = \frac{a_0}{\Delta g_{zp}(r_0)} = \frac{c_0^2}{4\sqrt{M_{Gx}G a_U}}, \quad \text{and while the border-line radius where Newtonian gravitation is equal to the MOND acceleration fit parameter interpreted as the zero-point quantum fluctuation acceleration is: } r_0 = \sqrt{\frac{M_{Gx}G}{a_U}}.$$

variables is non-zero.

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Hence the total gravitational acceleration is:

$$g_{EQGM}(r) = g_N(r) + \Delta g_{zpeFE}(r). \quad (129)$$

Below, Fig. 2a (linear scale) and Fig. 2b (double logarithmic scale) do exhibit comparisons between the Newtonian law, the empirical MOND models, and the EQGM model, demonstrating the congruence between the empirical MOND and the analytical EQGM model, while EQGM delivers slightly higher accelerations. The mass is assumed to be for a typical galaxy containing 10^{11} sun mass $M_{Gx} = 1.988 \cdot 10^{41} \text{ kg}$.

FIG. 2a. Comparison of gravitational acceleration $g [m/s^2]$ depending on center distance $r [m]$ at a typical galaxy calculated from Newton's law (circles), the MOND1 (squares) and MOND2 (rhombs) formulas, and based on quantum zero-point acceleration law from EQGM (crosses), respectively. Furthermore, a_0 MOND fit parameter is shown (dashed line).

In case of more complex settings like for a mass object in the range of several galaxies, like in a galaxy cluster, the simple deep-MOND formula may not be applied. Moreover, the total gravitation effect on the mass object must be calculated from vectors with different directions and dependencies on $(1/r)$ versus $(1/r^2)$, which is left for further study.

To summarize, the EQGM approach from this work provides an analytical explanation approach for the empirical observations and MOND models on galaxy behavior.

A DM assumption in terms of additional "physical matter" to cause additional gravitational acceleration

in the outer regimes of galaxies is not required here due to zero-point quantum fluctuation acceleration acting on all mass objects being confined in the Universe.

FIG. 2b. Acceleration functions as shown and already described in FIG. 2a above but displayed in double logarithmic scale.

B. Explanation for Dark Energy and accelerated expansion of the Universe

The zero-point energy described above causes a repulsive (i.e. expansive) pressure in the Universe as contained in an outside vacuum, while acting against the attracting gravitational forces. Accordingly, this energy is a candidate to explain DE.

At the border of the universe at $r = R_U$ the pressure is made up by the kinetic zero-point energy of the mass object fluid in the Universe itself. The DE is appearing in the Universe as the kinetic expansion energy of masses as perceived by any observer witnessing Hubble inflation. The radial expansive pressure is:

$$P_{exp} = \frac{-W_{zpU}}{(4/3)\pi R_U^3} = \frac{-M_U c_0^2}{(4/3)\pi R_U^3} = -\rho_U c_0^2. \quad (130)$$

The gravitational, deflationary pressure calculated according to the hydrostatic approach is:

$$P_{gU}(R_U) = \int_0^{R_U} \rho(r) g_U(r) dr = \frac{1}{2} \rho_U c_0^2. \quad (131)$$

Hence an effective pressure of:

$$\Delta P = P_{exp} + P_{gU} = P_{exp} + P_{gN} + P_{gzp} = -\frac{1}{2} \rho_U c_0^2 = -7.529 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{N}{m^2}, \quad (132)$$

acting like a net „negative gravitation“ and an acceleration for the scale parameter a do result at the

boarder of the Universe as:

$$\Delta g = \frac{\Delta P}{M_U} = \frac{-3c_0^2}{2R_U} = -3g_{zp} = -3.078 \cdot 10^{-10} \frac{m}{s^2},$$

and

$$\ddot{a} = \frac{-\Delta g}{R_U} = 7.026 \cdot 10^{-37} s^{-2}. \quad (133)$$

Related to the notation used in the current Standard Model of Cosmology (Λ -CDM model) with w being the DE factor in the equation of state, this results to $w = -1$ in line with observations from [10] and with ESA Planck results [11], as well as with WMAP findings [14].

From the EQGM - considering classical Newton and on top zero-point gravitational acceleration - the DE density is $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.666$, two-fold the gravitational energy density attached to the mass of the Universe at $\Omega_M = 0.333$, if energy densities from radiation Ω_r and curvature of space Ω_K can be neglected.

ESA Planck results from Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) analysis exhibit $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.685$ and $\Omega_M = 0.315$ (± 0.007), if Ω_K is set to zero. With the extended Λ -CDM model, Ω_K is found around 0.025 (± 0.02) [11], with this EQGM results being in line for Ω_M and Ω_Λ .

For the case that energy densities were analyzed based on observations of galaxy lensing, i.e. with underlying gravitation effects also beyond the zero-point gravitational acceleration, ESA Planck [11] and WMAP results [14] are found in the regimes around $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.73$ and $\Omega_M = 0.27$. This points to a case where zero-point gravitational acceleration partial pressure

$$P_{gzp} = g_{zp} \frac{M_U}{4\pi R_U^2} = \frac{c_0^2}{2R_U} \frac{M_U}{4\pi R_U^2} = \frac{\rho_U}{6} c_0^2$$

might have to be skipped in calculation of ΔP above, since not dominating the observation. This would lead to a ratio of 3:1 for Ω_Λ (75%): Ω_M (25%) from EQGM.

But this needs further study, as well as the general systematic observational tension found in Hubble constant obtained from CMB versus from galaxy populations – see comprehensive review and discussion in [22].

However, latest results from Dark-Energy Survey (DES) [23] do even result to $\Omega_M = 0.339$ (± 0.03) and $w = -1$ very well in line with the holistic approach on the Universe described by EQGM.

To conclude, the EQGM can also provide an explanation for DE, within the relative precision of currently available observations. According to EQGM the total on top energy appearing in the Universe is:

$$W_{Uzp} = M_U c_0^2 = DE = (DM + VM) c_0^2 = 5.301 \cdot 10^{70} J. \quad (134)$$

Thus, the equivalent mass associated with this DE is the mass of the Universe M_U itself, containing DM and Visible Matter (VM).

C. Implications on and from the Gravity constant

Comparing the two different expressions derived in section II.A Eq. (5) and Eq. (8) for the zero-point acceleration a_U , an analytical formula for the gravity constant was found: $G = \frac{R_U c_0^2}{M_U}$. Thus gravity “constant” appears as a parameter, depending on radius and mass of the Universe. At least there is no requirement for the more exceptional case that it be a fundamental constant of nature. Hence G will change over time in a non-stationary Universe if the ratio R_U/M_U is not constant. This would feedback on its evolution, leading to non-linear effects. However, regardless of how R_U and M_U evolve, they cancel out in the calculation for the kinetic zero-point energy²⁰ of a mass in the Universe, that thus will always be identical to the value of its rest energy.

Due to the problem of DM and DE the exact value of mass M_U was unknown so far. However, since I found the formula above which is confirmed by the identity of calculated and observed zero-point acceleration, the mass M_U can be calculated out of it if a value for radius R_U is given.

To what extend would mankind have been able to observe a change in G over the course of research, i.e., time T_{GO} from years 1798 to 2023? The answer is: Not at all, assuming a change of its radius based on the Hubble expansion [11] of: $\Delta G = H_0 T_{GO} = 1.551 \cdot 10^{-8}$, with $H_0 = 67.4 \frac{km/s}{Mpc} = 2.184 \cdot 10^{-18} s^{-1}$, since preciseness of measured values for G being three orders of magnitude less [4].

The formula for G is also the definition of the event horizon of a stationary finite low density black hole. However, which is different from a dark star black hole that would exhibit a Schwarzschild radius r_S as its event horizon, which is double the value of r_{bh} [24]. Hence mass of the Universe M_U also might be increased from outside of it. Looking at the critical mass density required to form a black hole, the Universe is below this regarding its average density:

$$\rho_U = \frac{M_U}{(4/3)\pi R_U^3} = 1.675 \cdot 10^{-27} kgm^{-3}, \text{ versus:}$$

$$\rho_{Cr} = \frac{3H_0^2}{8\pi} = 8.533 \cdot 10^{-27} kgm^{-3}.$$

D. Gravitational zero-point fluctuations

With the EQGM derived above, zero-point kinetic energy of a mass in the Universe has a value equal to its rest energy but appearing on top. It can be understood in a classical manner as gravitational self-energy rooted in the potential of the Universe, and in a quantum mechanical view as being required from the Heisenberg uncertainty due to confinement in its potential. However, how can this relatively high on top energy and the attached zero-point acceleration for mass objects be understood and why is it not observed directly? Key to understand is the quite short Planck-time scale t_{Pl}/ξ introduced in Eq. (7) in which uncertainty is taking place. In case of absence of other forces, we can also calculate the fluctuation kinetic energy W_{fluc} and a zero-point fluctuation distance r_{fluc} that is caused for the non-localized mass, with $\sqrt{2}\sigma_{xU} = R_U$, while probability distribution is spread across the Universe:

$$W_{fluc} = \frac{1}{2} m \left(g_{zp} \frac{t_{Pl}}{\xi} \right)^2, \text{ and } r_{fluc} = \frac{1}{2} g_{zp} \left(\frac{t_{Pl}}{\xi} \right)^2. \quad (135)$$

With using Eqs. (5), (6), (8), this can be written as:

$$W_{fluc}(m) = \frac{\hbar m_{Pl}^2 c_0}{8mR_U M_U} = \frac{W_{Gh} m_{Pl}^2}{8 m M_U} = m c_0^2 \frac{r_{fluczp}}{2R_U},$$

$$\text{yielding: } W_{fluc}(m_{Pl}) = 3.329 \cdot 10^{-115} J. \quad (136)$$

Alternatively, expressed as a fluctuation temperature:

$$T_{fluc}(m) = \frac{W_{fluc}(m)}{k_B}, \text{ e.g. yielding:}$$

$$T_{fluc}(m_{Pl}) = 2.411 \cdot 10^{-92} K. \quad (137)$$

And for the fluctuation radius²¹:

$$r_{fluc}(m) = \frac{\hbar m_{Pl}^2}{4M_U c_0 m^2} = \frac{r_{gBr} m_{Pl}^2}{4 m M_U} = \frac{(\lambda_C(m))^2}{4R_U}, \text{ yielding:}$$

$$r_{fluc}(m_{Pl}) = 1.491 \cdot 10^{-97} m, \quad (138)$$

demonstrating that this fluctuation energy is too tiny to be observed directly. However, energy density of the fluctuations in the spherical shell with thickness $r_{fluc}/3$ is identical as for the zero-point energy of the mass object related to half the volume of the entire Universe:

$$W_{fluc} = \frac{W_{fluc}}{4\pi R_U^2 (r_{fluc}/3)} = \frac{m c_0^2}{(8/3)\pi R_U^3} = W_{zp}. \quad (139)$$

Accordingly, the ratio of fluctuation energy to

²⁰ Based on Eq. (3) while inserting the formula for G from Eq. (9) and confirmed by Eq. (11) not depending on G .

²¹ Note, that this is identical to the minimum possible radius hypothesized for the Universe as given in Eq. (54).

fluctuation radius of a mass object is identical to the ratio of its rest energy to the diameter of the Universe:

$$\frac{W_{fluc}}{r_{fluc}} = \frac{W_0}{2R_U}. \quad (140)$$

E. Quantization of time for a mass

Out of the Heisenberg uncertainty, there must be a non-zero minimum for time uncertainty for a mass object. This can be understood as time to have a ‘‘granularity’’, raising the question how to interpret this in physical processes as such. If we assume, that any physical interaction of a mass with its environment requires time to evolve, it can be hypothesized that the granularity of time be what has been applied in Eq. (7) already:

$$\sqrt{2} \sigma_{tU} \geq \frac{t_{Pl}}{\xi} = \frac{t_{Pl} m_{Pl}}{m} = \frac{\hbar}{m c_0^2} = \tau_{fluc} = \frac{\lambda_C(m)}{c_0}. \quad (141)$$

For example, for an electron this would result to a granularity in the range of 10^{-21} s, and for the smallest particle known so far, the Neutrino, it will be at least in the range of 10^{-1} s.

For the minimum mass of an object required to exist in the Universe, as derived in Eq. (26), we gain:

$$\sqrt{2} \sigma_{tU}(m_{minU}) = \frac{\hbar}{R_U c_0^2} = 46.65 \text{ bn yrs}. \quad (142)$$

This appears to be logical in the sense that a mass in the Universe can only be noticed if it at least once in the time the Universe is existing²² would become part of any physical process.

F. Zero-gravitation and degree of quantization

Considering more compact potential wells than the Universe and with homogeneous mass density, there must be a limit where gravon ground state energy level will become equal or higher than the depth of the respective gravitational potential well. With Eq. (60) this means that the gravitation effect of a mass object ($m; r_m$) in a homogeneous mass density ‘‘cloud’’ ($M_C; R_C$) would vanish, if:

$$W_{Gr0} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{2R_C} \geq \frac{1}{2} \frac{m M_C G}{R_C} = \frac{1}{2} m c_0^2 \eta, \text{ with:}$$

$$\eta = \frac{R_U M_C}{R_C M_U}. \quad (143)$$

While $\eta = \gamma - 1$ is a scale factor to re-normalize zero-point energy of mass in the Universe towards the interaction of mass with the cloud. γ is the Lorentz factor, i.e. to assume a value of 2 if radius and mass of the Universe would be applied.

Reformulating the inequation yields:

$$m M_C \leq \frac{\hbar M_U}{c_0 R_U} = m_{Pl}^2 = (2.176 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ kg})^2. \quad (144)$$

This means, for an object with the product of its mass and cloud's mass being less than the square of the Planck-mass, the gravitation effect must be expected to vanish.

A different setup with hyperbolic potential arises for two mass objects ($m; r_m$) and ($M; R_M$) interacting over a distance $d > r_m + R_M$. The non-relativistic gravitational Bohr model²³ from Eq. (17) at ground state ($n = 1$) yields:

$$r_{gB} = \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2 M G} \equiv d, \text{ thus: } m^2 M = \frac{\hbar^2}{d G}. \quad (145)$$

From this, three cases do arise:

(a) Significant quantization effects should be observed, if distance of mass objects is in the range of the gravitational Bohr radius. For example, for a distance of $d = 6 \text{ cm}$ between a mass of 0.001 kg and a neutron. Another example are two identical mass objects with $1.4 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ kg}$ at this distance.

(b) For a distance less than the gravitational Bohr radius gravitational force should vanish since energy cannot be decreased below ground state.

(c) For a distance significantly larger than the gravitational Bohr radius, the gravitation effect should approach a continuum, i.e. quantization cannot be resolved in observation anymore.

To conclude, zero-gravitation and quantization effects should be considered for formation processes between particles converging out of gas, dust, and micro particles, which is for further study²⁴.

G. Entropy in the Universe

As discussed in section III.C, the size parameters ($R_U; M_U$) of the Universe also relate to a low-density

²² Obviously, this is not the age of the Universe since it has expanded from presumed big bang and it is $R_U > R_H$ today. However, the argument for a mass to become part of any physical process at least once needs to apply to the entire Universe.

²³ To use the non-relativistic formulas, $mM < m_{Pl}^2$ must apply, as in the three case examples here. The implications for the relativistic case with $mM \geq m_{Pl}^2$ are considered for example in Appendix C.

²⁴ Apart from this, objects will experience gravitation effects from all other objects in the Universe, also including the holistic zero-point acceleration as described above.

black hole. With this, a Bekenstein-Hawking-Entropy [27], [28] given by:

$$S_{bh} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\ln(2) k_B c_0^3 A_{bh}}{4 \hbar G} \quad (146)$$

can be derived, while for the Universe the surface of the black hole is: $A_{bhU} = 4\pi R_U^2$. Using the minimum for a mass to exist in the Universe from Eq. (52), as well as Eq. (9) found for G and Eq. (20) for the ghton energy, entropy can be formulated as:

$$S_{bhU} = \frac{\pi^2}{2} \ln(2) k_B \frac{M_U}{m_{minU}} = 3.469 \cdot 10^{100} \frac{J}{K}. \quad (147)$$

In this, maximum entropy [29] in the Universe appears based on the maximum number of possible states given by the ratio of total mass in the Universe and the minimum possible particle mass. Due to the Einstein equivalence principle this can also be expressed by the ratio of the DE and the minimum gravitational energy realized in the ghton quantum:

$$S_{bhU} = \frac{\pi^2}{2} \ln(2) k_B \frac{DE}{W_{GhU}}, \text{ with:} \\ DE = M_U c_0^2 \text{ and } W_{GhU} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{R_U} = m_{minU} c_0^2. \quad (148)$$

In this the factor $\ln(2) k_B$ makes the difference between mathematical and physical entropy: In information theoretic terms, the information entropy of a system is the amount of "missing" information needed to determine a microstate for a given macrostate [33]. Regarding the information entropy of the Universe, this can be interpreted as the information about the mass objects contained²⁵:

$$\mathcal{H}_U = \frac{\pi^2}{2} \frac{M_U}{m_{minU}} = 3.625 \cdot 10^{123} \text{ bit} \quad (149)$$

For the temperature as a black body, a Hawking-radiation from the black hole was proposed in [28], with:

$$T_H = \frac{\hbar c_0^3}{8\pi G M k_B}. \quad (150)$$

Again, for the Universe with the formula for G and the ghton energy it is found that:

$$T_{HU} = \frac{W_{Gh(RU)}}{8\pi k_B} = 2.080 \cdot 10^{-31} K. \quad (151)$$

Hence the temperature of the black body radiation for the Universe shall be based on the ghton energy,

²⁵ This can be thought of as coding a bit sequence of length \mathcal{H}_U (without the spherical length scale factor resulting from GRT as $\frac{\pi^2}{2}$) representing the mass of a mass object by a number of consecutive 0-bits each standing for a ghton mass equivalent quantum contributing to the mass of the object, followed by a sequence of 1-bits representing the description for the next mass object and so on and so forth for all ghtons and mass objects that sum up to the total mass contained in the Universe considered as a black hole. In general, this is the information lost about mass objects if these do fall into a black hole behind the event horizon.

which appears to be consistent with the entropy derived above.

With this, reconsidering black holes in general, gravitational quantum particles to be emitted from them can be assumed to have an energy of:

$$W_{Gh}(R_{bh}) = \frac{\hbar c_0}{R_{bh}}. \quad (152)$$

Looking back to the energy of quantum fluctuations in the Universe derived in Eq. (136) and comparing them to the Hawking temperature from Eq. (151), while using Eq. (26) for the minimum particle mass in the Universe, as well as Eq. (9), we yield:

$$T_{fluc}(m) = T_{HU} \pi \frac{m_{Umin}}{m} = T_{HU} \pi \frac{W_{Gh(RU)}}{W_0(m)} \quad (155)$$

This means quantum fluctuation temperature for a mass in the Universe as described by the EQGM directly relates to the Hawking temperature.

Finally, I want to uncover another path from the zero-point acceleration on mass objects in the Universe to the quantum gravitation with ghton exchange particles as derived in the EQGM.

In the year 1976 W. G. Unruh showed that an observer with uniform acceleration a will experience to be embedded in a particle bath with the Unruh temperature [34] defined as:

$$T_{Un} = \frac{\hbar a}{2\pi k_B c_0}. \quad (156)$$

Setting the Unruh temperature equal to the Hawking temperature of the Universe taken from Eq. (151), the resulting Unruh uniform acceleration is half of the zero-point acceleration for an arbitrary mass object given by Eq. (5) and Eq. (8) in the EQGM:

$$a_{Un} = \frac{c_0^2}{4R_U} = \frac{a_U}{2}. \quad (157)$$

From this is can be concluded that the ghton particles in the Universe make up an Unruh particle bath and consequently are required already out of the uniform zero-point quantum gravitational acceleration in the Universe. This also links back to section II.C regarding the ghton bath interpretations following out of the energy quantization of gravitation derived there.

H. Quantum origin of gravitation and inertial Equivalence Principle

A generalized law for gravitational energy and acceleration for two mass objects m and M separated by a distance r in the Universe can be described as:

$$W_{gpot}(m, M, r) = \frac{-m}{r} = -\eta_G m c_0^2, \text{ with:} \quad (158)$$

$$\eta_G = \frac{R_U}{r} \frac{M}{M_U}, \text{ since } G = \frac{R_U c_0^2}{M_U}.$$

With η_G being the scale factor to re-normalize respective confinement of mass objects and size of mass related to the properties of the Universe.

Now I consider the two mass objects as confining each other in the Universe and describe them in Heisenberg uncertainty relations used as equations, hence realizing minimum energy possible. With uncertainties as:

$$\sigma_x = \frac{r}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ and } \sigma_p = \frac{p}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ yields: } p = \frac{\hbar}{r}. \quad (159)$$

$$\sqrt{2} \sigma_W = -W_{gpot} = W_{kin} = \eta_G m c_0^2 \text{ and} \quad (160)$$

$$\sqrt{2} \sigma_t = \frac{\hbar}{\eta_G m c_0^2}.$$

With this we gain for the force and acceleration²⁶ between the two mass objects:

$$\frac{\sigma_p}{\sigma_t} = F = ma = m \frac{\eta_G c_0^2}{r} = m c_0^2 \frac{R_U}{r^2} \frac{M}{M_U}. \quad (161)$$

The force is attractive since momentum p increases/decreases with decreasing/increasing distance r due to Heisenberg uncertainty relation in Eq. (159).

The perspective for gravitation is, that it seems to originate from an instability contained in the quantum mechanical uncertainty, maximizing confined momentum, and minimizing distance between mass objects.

This has also already been shown in section II.C.5 with the immanent quantum interaction found between two mass objects out of their joint wave function applied in the KGE and SE.

Thus, gravitation appears as based on inertia, explaining the equivalence principle of inertial and gravitational acceleration. Hence, we find no such specific property like a „gravitational acceleration“ being different from inertia.

²⁶ For an object on the surface of the Earth for example the expected acceleration value is gained:

$$a_E = \frac{\eta_E c_0^2}{R_E} = c_0^2 \frac{R_U}{R_E^2} \frac{M_E}{M_U} = \left(2.998 \cdot 10^8 \frac{m}{s}\right)^2 \frac{4.380 \cdot 10^{26} m \cdot 5.972 \cdot 10^{24} kg}{(6.366 \cdot 10^6 m)^2 \cdot 5.899 \cdot 10^{53} kg} = 9.835 \frac{m}{s^2}.$$

²⁷ For an average nucleon in the atomic nucleus arithmetic mean values of proton and neutron mass and radius are taken: $m_N = 1837 m_e$ and $r_N = 1.122 fm$ - see Eq. (162). Note that in textbooks values in the range of $r_N = 0.9 \dots 1.4 fm$ are given, mainly depending on the number of nucleons in the atomic nucleus and constellations analyzed [35], [36], [37].

I. Quantum confinement in atomic nuclei

1. Potential energy in the atomic nucleus

Revisiting section III.G and Eq. (60), a further specific case with $W_{Gr0} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{2R} \gg \frac{1}{2} \frac{mMG}{R} = \frac{1}{2} m c_0^2 \eta$, meaning that required quantum mechanical zero-point energy in confinement being by far larger than the depth of the related gravitational potential from a homogenous mass distribution, shall be analyzed.

In this context, I want to consider the basic principles of the atomic nucleus and the fundamental strong interaction force effect between nucleons.

Based on Eq. (60) the kinetic gravon energy - i.e., the negative gravitational potential energy - for an average nucleon²⁷ seen as confined in the potential well of the atomic nucleus with radius R_A and a homogenous mass distribution is:

$$W_{GrN} = W_{kinN} = -W_{gpotN} =$$

$$W_{0N} \left[\frac{3\alpha_A}{2} - \frac{n_{Gr}^2}{2} \left(\frac{W_{Gh}(R_A)}{W_{0N}} \right)^2 \right],$$

with: $\alpha_A = \frac{R_U}{R_A} \frac{M_A}{M_U}$, and: $R_A = r_N N_N^{1/3}$, $M_A = m_N N_N$,
 $W_{0N} = m_N c_0^2 = 938.9 MeV$, and:
 $r_N = 1.122 fm$. (162)

The gravon quantum number n_{Gr} will depend on the number of nucleons, while the law is different from the atomic shell model for electrons due to further effects to be considered in the atomic nucleus [35]. However,

it can be shown to approximately follow $n_{Gr} \sim \left(\frac{N_N}{g_{si}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$, with $g_{si} = 2$ due to the isospin degeneracy of the deuteron, i.e., of the proton-neutron pairs in the atomic nucleus. Hence gravon energy in Eq. (162) does almost not dependent on the number of nucleons N_N . While the first term with re-normalization factor η is neglectable due to tininess of atomic nuclei mass as compared to the mass of the Universe, from simplifying it results in an Eq. (163):

$$W_{kinN} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{[W_{Gh}(r_N)]^2}{g_{si}^2 W_{0N}} = -10.38 MeV = -W_{BN}.$$

This means, an average negative kinetic energy - i.e., binding energy W_{BN} - will be required to realize the

confinement.

Comparing this result to the established empirical Bethe-Weizsäcker (BW) droplet model [35], but for the volume and surface energy terms only - since Coulomb, asymmetry and pairing potential are not considered in the gravon energy - the binding energy is found to be in the correct range, e.g.: $W_{BW} = 9.31...11.42 \text{ MeV}$ for $N_N = 20...70$, since $W_{BW} = a_V + N_N^{-\frac{1}{3}}a_S$, with $a_V = 15.5 \text{ MeV}$ and $a_S = -16.8 \text{ MeV}$.

Looking at the Thomas-Fermi model for the Fermi energy in the potential of the atomic nucleus, it is [36],[37]:

$$W_{FA} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_N r_N^2} \left(\frac{9\pi}{4g_{si}} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} = \frac{(W_{GH}(r_N))^2}{2W_{0N}} \left(\frac{9\pi}{4g_{si}} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (164)$$

Yielding $W_{FA} = 60.67 \text{ MeV}$ without ($g_{si} = 1$) [37] and $W_{FA} = 38.22 \text{ MeV}$ with consideration ($g_{si} = 2$) [36] of isospin degeneration of nucleons, respectively.

Hence, in this work the Thomas-Fermi model is found to be directly based on the ratio of squared ghton energy and rest energy of the nucleon.

2. Binding energy from nucleon mass defect

Reflecting on the special situation, that the potential of the atomic nucleus and the strong interaction force between nucleons go hand in hand with a mass defect, the insights from the subsection above can serve as explanation. It appears to be that to realize the confinement in an atomic nucleus, a mass defect to deliver the missing kinetic energy must occur to the nucleons due to the laws of quantum mechanics, that otherwise would be violated. Setting up the expression for the mass defect:

$$\Delta m_N = \frac{W_{BN}}{c_0^2} = -\frac{W_{kinN}}{c_0^2} = \frac{1}{2g_{si}^{\frac{2}{3}}} \frac{\hbar^2}{r_N^2 m_N c_0^2}, \quad (165)$$

this can be shown by reformulation into a Heisenberg minimum uncertainty $\sigma_p \sigma_x = \frac{\hbar}{2}$ required, with:

$$\sigma_p = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta m_N m_N}{2}} c_0 \text{ and } \sigma_x = r_N, \text{ or:} \quad (166)$$

$$\sigma_W = \frac{\sigma_p^2}{2m_N} = \frac{\Delta m_N c_0^2}{4}, \text{ and:}$$

$$\sigma_t = \frac{\hbar}{2\sigma_W} = 1.27 \cdot 10^{-22} \text{ s.} \quad (167)$$

Furthermore, there must be limit for the mass defect, if a nucleon would be forced to the bottom of the potential well in the atomic nucleus, i.e., assuming a binding energy equal to the Fermi energy according to Eq. (61). This would lead to a minimum possible

radius for the nucleon and distance between nucleons of:

$$r_{N\min} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2g_{si}^{\frac{2}{3}}} \frac{\hbar^2}{m_N W_{FA}}} = r_N \left(\frac{9\pi}{4} \right)^{-\frac{1}{3}} = 0.585 \text{ fm.}$$

This is comparable with the range found in [35],[36],[37] for the point where the strong interaction force changes from being attractive to become repulsive.

3. Identity of pion and ghton

In the year 1934 H. Yukawa predicted the existence of a quantum exchange particle - called Meson and later named pion - to cause the strong interaction force effect within the deuteron, i.e., between the neutron and the proton as the key building block of the atomic nuclei [38].

The pion was confirmed by detection in the Earth's atmosphere in 1946 [39], and pion energy according to latest measurements as of the year 2020 taken from [40] is: $W_{\pi\pm} = 139.57 \text{ MeV}$.

With this work, the value of the pion energy is now found from an analytical approach to be identical to the ghton energy - which is the quantum gravitation exchange particle - of the potential well for the neutron and the proton confined within the volumetric radius of the deuteron R_{AD} :

$$W_{GH}(R_{AD}) = \frac{\hbar c_0}{R_{AD}} = 139.56 \text{ MeV, with:}$$

$$R_{AD} = r_{ND} 2^{1/3}. \quad (168)$$

In this the radius of the nucleons in the deuteron r_{ND} is made up by the average value of half of the deuteron $r_d = 2.12562 \text{ fm}$, to the degree as determined according to [42], and the sum of the root-mean-square electric charge radius of the proton $r_{pE} = 0.8409 \text{ fm}$ and the root-mean-square charge radius of the neutron $r_n = 0.341 \text{ fm}$, both taken from [40]:

$$r_{ND} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{r_d}{2} + (r_{pE} + r_n) \right) = 1.122 \text{ fm.} \quad (169)$$

This average can be understood as effective radius for a nucleon in the deuteron under the permanent exchange of pions between the proton and the neutron, that make up the strong interaction force effect.

To summarize, the strong interaction force between nucleons in atomic nuclei can be derived and described analytically as a special case out of the quantum gravity model EQGM.

In this the potential well for the ghton is made up by the deuteron, and it is found that the ghton exhibits

identical energy as the pion, within the range of currently available precision in determination of the radius for the deuteron.

In addition, for the atomic nucleus, the gravon energy of the nucleons, i.e., their gravitational kinetic energy, is found to be equivalent to nucleon binding energies empirically found for the strong interaction force effect.

J. Coulomb interaction as quantum gravitational effect

As described in section II.C.5, elementary particles in the Universe do constitute quantum gravitational many-body systems. In this section this will be used to interpret the fundamental force of Coulombian / electrodynamic interaction first described in [56].

1. Relation of Coulombian and gravitational coupling parameters

It shall be analyzed whether the Coulombian aka Sommerfeld fine structure constant can be expressed without electrodynamic constants q and ϵ_0 , providing an understanding of the relation between quantized electrodynamic and gravitational forces.

This is inspired by the relations between microscopic and macroscopic worlds derived also in this work, namely the identity of gravitational and nuclear quantum effect forces.

Revisiting earlier considerations of H. Weyl (1919), A. Eddington (1931) and P. A. M. Dirac (1937) [55] on Large Number Hypotheses (LNHs), relating characteristic constants of the microscopic and macroscopic nature, a ratio found in this work is that of gravitational quantum fluctuation radius versus the radius of Universe to fluctuation energy versus rest energy – see section III.D and Eq. (140): $\frac{W_{fluc}}{r_{fluc}} = \frac{W_0}{2R_U}$.

Based on considerations from [53] about the relation of the size of the Universe and the electron, and comparing to the ratio of the Coulombian and the gravitational coupling parameters, a LNH is:

$$\frac{F_C}{F_g} = \frac{\alpha_C}{\alpha_{Gep}} \approx \frac{2R_U}{\lambda_{Ce}} \quad \text{with: } \lambda_{Ce} = \frac{\hbar}{m_e c_0} \quad (170)$$

Hence, resulting in that the Sommerfeld fine-structure constant as the Coulombian coupling parameter between an electron in the ground-state at a proton (hydrogen atom) $\alpha_C = \alpha_{Cep}$ can be formulated completely without Coulombian / electrodynamic

constants, purely based on the gravitational coupling parameter between an electron (e) and a proton (p).

Out of this work the LNH can now be proven on analytical basis, from three approaches applied to fundamental particles:

(a) Consideration of required vs. available states

With Eq. (67) and Eq. (70) the Coulombian coupling parameter can be written in the inertial system of the Universe (U) as an Eq. (171):

$$\alpha_{CU} = 2n_{Grmax}(m_e)\alpha_{Gep} = 2[n_{Grmax}(m_e)]^2 \frac{m_p}{M_U},$$

with Eq. (22) and considering Eq. (52):

$$n_{Grmax}(m_e) = \frac{R_U m_e c_0}{\hbar} = \frac{m_e c_0^2}{m_{minU} c_0^2} = \frac{W_0(m_e)}{W_{GhU}}. \quad (172)$$

Moreover, the gravitational and Coulombian coupling constants contain the same ratio: The maximum quantum gravitational number for electrons $n_{Grmax}(m_e)$ to fit into the Universe based on their reduced Compton wavelength.

The interpretation I propose for this is as follows: The ratio is the excess occupancy factor ζ_{es} already described in Eq. (75), since the number of required quantum gravitational states for the many-body electron system exceeds their number of available states in the Universe.

$$\zeta_{ese} = \frac{N_{rse}}{N_{ase}} = \frac{N_{eU}^2}{2[n_{Grmax}(m_e)]^3} \quad (173)$$

Following this approach, and setting $\zeta_{ese} = 2n_{Grmax}(m_e)$, the number of electrons in the Universe would be:

$$N_{eU} = 2[n_{Grmax}(m_e)]^2 = \frac{2R_U^2}{\lambda_{Ce}^2} = 2.573 \cdot 10^{78} \quad (173a)$$

Since the Universe is assumed homogenous at large, all energy levels must be occupied with same probability since at large we find electrons equally distributed along all possible radii i.e. locations and hence energies according to Fig. 1 within the Universe. To accommodate further electrons the gravitation energy will be added along the quantized radii allowed as an “excess quantization” stacking the energies with multiple ζ_{es} in the quantum confinement potential well made up by the Universe and its radius.

According to the approach, it follows²⁸:

²⁸ Note that a single electron and proton do not interact gravitationally since their ground-state gravitational Bohr radius is larger than the radius of the Universe and their mass product is less than Planck mass squared - see zero-gravitation as described in section III.F.

$$\alpha_{CU} = \alpha_{cep} = \frac{N_{eU} m_p}{M_U} \text{ and: } \alpha_{Gep} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{N_{eU}}{2}} m_p}{M_U}. \quad (174)$$

(b) *Consideration of multi-particle KGE solution*

The same result for the ratio of Coulombian and gravitational coupling parameters was derived out of the KGE/SE solution for many-body systems as described in Eq. (111).

(c) *Consideration of the Dirac Sea picture*

Another confirmation for the ratio of Coulombian and gravitational coupling is gained out of relating the fundamental particles of Coulombian and gravitational interaction: With Eq. (172) the relation between the photon, as the exchange particle for the electrodynamic force related to the electron, and the ghton, as the exchange particle for the gravitational force related to the minimum possible mass in the Universe, can be written as an Eq. (175):

$$\frac{2W_{Ph}(\lambda_C(m_e))}{W_{Gh}(\lambda_C(m_{minU}))} = \frac{2m_e c_0^2}{m_{minU} c_0^2} = \frac{\alpha_C}{\alpha_{Gep}} = 2.268 \cdot 10^{39}.$$

With the coupling parameters α for the coupling between electron and proton for the electrodynamic and gravitational force, respectively. This relation implies add/remove processes of fundamental particles representing the Coulomb and gravitational interaction to the Universe based on the picture of the Dirac sea [54] and “ghoton bath” as described in section III.G.

If an electron is annihilated with a positron from the Dirac sea, it is removed and hence Coulomb-decoupled from the Universe, while two photons with the rest energy of the fermionic electron-positron particle-antiparticle pair are created instead into the “photon bath” of the Universe.

If from a mass object the minimum possible mass m_{minU} is annihilated and hence removed from the Universe, a ghton boson will be created and set free to the “ghoton bath”, meaning that gravitational energy of the mass object is reduced accordingly.

The same applies vice versa for adding respective fundamental particles.

Revisiting section II.C.1, where the Bohr model was introduced also for gravitational quantization, the Coulombian interaction can be described analogous to

the gravitational formula containing the ghton. Using Eq. (18) and Eq. (19) for the Universe with $M = M_U$, we can set:

$$W_{Ckin} = \frac{(m c_0^2)^3}{2n^2 W_{PhU}^2} = W_{Cr}(n), \text{ with:} \\ W_{PhU} = \frac{W_0(m_e)}{\alpha_C} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{r_e}. \quad (176)$$

Meaning the “universal Photon” W_{PhU} is based on the classical electron radius²⁹ given by:

$$r_e = \lambda_C(m_{PhU}) = \lambda_C\left(\frac{m_e}{\alpha_C}\right). \quad (177)$$

In other words: The universal Photon exhibits the wavelength equal to the perimeter of the electron as resulting from its Coulombian self-energy.

To summarize this section, the hypothesis is, that the electrodynamic force can be unified as a quantum mechanically rooted force, same as for gravitation and the nuclear force already shown based on the EQGM out of this work.

(d) *Relations for basic Coulombian parameters*

With the results from the section above the radius of the Universe can now be described based on constants and parameters of nature as:

$$R_U = \frac{\hbar q^2}{8\pi \epsilon_0 c_0 m_e^2 m_p G} = \frac{\lambda_C(m_e) \alpha_{cep}}{2 \alpha_{Gep}} \quad (178)$$

Furthermore, from the relations above, the proton mass can be expressed as:

$$m_p = \frac{q^2}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \frac{\hbar M_U}{2m_e^2 c_0^3 R_U^2} = \alpha_C \left(\frac{\lambda_C(m_e)}{R_U}\right)^2 \frac{M_U}{2} \quad (179)$$

The elementary electric charge q can be expressed without any specific Coulombian/electrodynamic constants or parameters as:

$$e = \frac{q}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0}} = -\sqrt{4\pi N_{eU} \frac{m_p}{M_U}}. \quad (180)$$

Out of the definition of the Coulombian coupling constant and with Eqs. (171) and (172) we get:

$$e = \frac{q}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0}} = -\sqrt{4\pi \hbar c_0 \alpha_C} = -\sqrt{8\pi \hbar c_0 \frac{m_e^2 m_p}{m_{minU}^2 M_U}},$$

or alternatively formulated for q as:

$$q = -\sqrt{\frac{8\pi m_p m_e^2 c_0 R_U^2}{\hbar \mu_0 M_U}}, \quad (181)$$

²⁹ The classical electron radius is known as its Coulomb self-energy from setting the Coulomb energy between two elementary charges to the rest energy of the electron: $W_C(r_e) = \frac{q^2}{4\pi \epsilon_0 r_e} \equiv W_0(m_e)$.

with the magnetic field constant, by definition as an SI unit until year 2019 set at a fixed value of $\mu_0 = 4\pi(10^{-7})NA^{-2}$.

2. Coulombian parameters of Fermions

To further validate the hypothesis that the electrodynamic force is rooted in quantum gravitation for many-particle systems, the electrodynamic self-coupling parameter also for other fermions (up- and down quarks, electron-neutrinos) that appear in stable configurations in the Universe shall be analyzed.

The general approach for a fermion particle x is: $\alpha_{Gxx} = \frac{m_x^2}{m_{minU}M_U}$, and for the maximum radial quantum number: $n_{Grmax}(m_x) = \frac{R_U}{\lambda_C(m_x)} = \frac{R_U m_x c_0}{\hbar}$.

For the excess quantization factor based on the spherical maximum quantum numbers according to Eq. (173) it is: $\zeta_{esx} = \frac{N_{rsx}}{N_{asx}} = \frac{N_x U^2}{2n_{Grmax}(m_x)^3}$, (182)

and hence for the electrodynamic coupling with $\lambda_{GhU} = R_U$:

$$\alpha_{Cxx} = \zeta_{esx} \alpha_{Gxx} = \frac{N_x U^2}{2m_x m_{Pl}^2} \left(\frac{\hbar}{R_U c_0} \right)^3 = \frac{N_x U^2 W_{GhU}^3}{2W_0(m_x)W_0(m_{Pl})^2} = \frac{N_x U^2 \lambda_C(m_x) \lambda_C(m_{Pl})^2}{2\lambda_{GhU}^3}. \quad (183)$$

By relating Coulombian coupling parameters it is yielded for the coupling between two particles of the same kind versus α_{Cee} , which has the same value as α_{Cep} , and with Eq. (66):

$$\frac{\alpha_{Cxx}}{\alpha_{Cee}} = \frac{q_x^2}{q^2}, \text{ hence: } |q_x| = |q| \sqrt{\frac{\alpha_{Cxx}}{\alpha_{Cep}}}, \quad (184)$$

This is with using Eq. (182):

$$|q_x| = |q| \frac{N_x U m_e}{N_{eU} m_x} \quad (185)$$

This is only valid for fundamental particles (leptons and quarks), it is not valid for composed elementary particles like e.g. the proton or the neutron.

Let's initially assume, that the Universe is electrically neutral, i.e. the number of electrons and protons to be identical: $N_{pU} = N_{eU}$, and that the number of neutrons equals the number of protons in the Universe: $N_{nU} = N_{pU}$. This also would mean that in this case the number of up- and down quarks is identical, since stable free quarks have not been observed to date.

(a) Stable fundamental particles – First generation quarks

To analyze the first generation quarks and their

electrical charge, their number per baryon is required, which is $\kappa_b = 3$, while the number of up- and down quarks per proton and neutron are: $\kappa_{pu} = 2$; $\kappa_{pd} = 1$; $\kappa_{nu} = 1$; $\kappa_{nd} = 2$.

Hence the number of up- and down quarks calculates as:

$$N_{uU} = N_{pU} \kappa_{pu} + N_{nU} \kappa_{nu}, \text{ and} \quad (186)$$

$$N_{dU} = N_{pU} \kappa_{pd} + N_{nU} \kappa_{nd}, \quad (187)$$

Now applying Eq. (185) delivers:

$$|q_u| = 0.66652037q, \text{ and } |q_d| = 0.319374344q,$$

which needs to be compared to the nominal values of $q_u = -2/3q$ and $q_d = 1/3q$.

The mass values for the up- and down quarks applied above are taken according to 2014 data [41], with: $m_u = 2.3 \pm 1.2 \text{ MeV}/c_0^2$, and $m_d = 4.8 \pm 0.8 \text{ MeV}/c_0^2$.

If taking latest available data from Data Particle Group 2020 [40], which is the same given still in the year 2022, with $m_u = 2.16 + 0.49/-0.26 \text{ MeV}/c_0^2$, and $m_d = 4.67 + 0.48/-0.17 \text{ MeV}/c_0^2$ this delivers:

$$|q_u| = 0.709720764q, \text{ and } |q_d| = 0.32826485q.$$

Given the significant variance in measured quark mass, the prediction of “electrical charge” by the quantum gravitational model out of this work as described above represents a good match.

The other way around, if one would assume that the latest measured mass values from the years 2020/2022 for the quarks were completely correct without variance, the ratio of electrons, protons and neutrons in the Universe would result to approximately: $N_{pU} = 86.26\% N_{eU}$ and $N_{nU} = 126.55\% N_{pU}$, while yielding a four-digit match in the decimals of charges:

$$|q_u| = 0.666617044q, \text{ and } |q_d| = 0.333396713q.$$

(b) Stable fundamental particles – Electron neutrinos

Now the validation of the gravitational excess state quantization model shall be done for the electron-neutrino. In [57] the electron neutrino and its antineutrino density in the Universe is assumed as 56 cm^{-3} each, i.e. resulting into $N_{\nu U} = 3.943 \cdot 10^{88}$ in total based on the radius of the Universe R_U used in the EQGM.

Applying Eq. (185) and Eq. (182) above as for the quarks, the resulting self-coupling parameter in the inertial system of the mass object (mo) calculates to: $\alpha_{\nu mo} = 4.876 \cdot 10^{22}$ as an ultra-relativistic result,

which needs to be transformed to the inertial system of the Universe (U). As lined out in section II.C.3 for the coupling parameter, in this case the coupling parameter is approaching $\alpha_{C\nu\nu U} \rightarrow 1$. With this and considering the relativistic increase of inertia of neutrino mass as $m_{\nu r} = \gamma_\nu m_\nu$ with Eq. (72) setting $\gamma_\nu = 1 + \alpha_{\nu\nu}$ and according to Eq. (184) it is:

$$|q_\nu| = q \sqrt{\frac{\alpha_{C\nu\nu U} m_p}{\alpha_{Cep} m_{\nu r}}} = 1.642 \cdot 10^{-5} q, \quad (188)$$

appearing that the neutrino is almost uncharged as to be expected. The neutrino rest mass assumed in this is $m_\nu = 2.14 \cdot 10^{-37} kg$, i.e. the current upper limit for its mass [40]. However, also smaller values for this mass will not change the charge value in the calculation above, as the result remains ultra-relativistic.

Note, that if the number of electron neutrinos would not be by far higher than the number of the other fermions, with the otherwise moderate relativistic setting the Electron neutrino could be concluded to carry massive electric charge.

To summarize, the neutrino is found to have an ultra-relativistic degeneracy with neglectable electric charge due to its low mass, and thus large Compton wavelength, so that there are relatively few quantum states available for it in the Universe.

(c) Non-stable elementary particles

Finally, I want to consider non-stable, temporary quarks and leptons found in the second and third generations of fundamental particles and respective baryons they do compose.

To interpret many-body quantum statistics in the case of non-stable, temporary elementary particles, their existence needs to be aligned with the statistics in exchange with the other identical elementary particles. However the information about these statistics can only propagate in space with the speed of light and hence can only effect a particle's environment within a sphere with the radius of: $r_{inx} = \tau_{Lx} c_0$ and an increasing volume after creation of the particle as: $V_{inx} = \frac{4}{3} \pi (\tau_{Lx} c_0)^3$

To cope with this, I want to consider local spatial particle densities n_x instead of total numbers N_x in the entire Universe. Thus, densities might differ across the Universe, but which is not relevant for the local many-body statistics since they are in isolated spheres given

by their radii of influence. Furthermore – as already with the electron-neutrino above – relativistic effects need to be considered since the second and third generation quarks and leptons are created and hence observed only in high energy settings. This is also due to their relatively short lifetimes, resulting into significant minimum energies following the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. However, despite relativistic effects the electrical charge will remain Lorentz invariant.

The most prominent lepton with the longest lifetime of $\tau_{L\mu} = 2.197 \cdot 10^{-6} s$ is the muon with a mass of $m_\mu \cong 206.8 m_e$ carrying a charge identical to the electron, as initially measured in the year 1937 [58]. The muon has been observed to build

- “Muonic atoms”, lasting for the lifetime of the muon, meaning muons can substitute shell electrons as for example in hydrogen, helium or copper. This means that electrons and muons do build a joint quantum statistic in the atom shell of copper³⁰.
- “Muonium atom” a lighter version of a hydrogen atom with the proton in the atomic nucleus substituted by an anti-muon, as discovered in the year 1960 [60].

Based on the existence of these atoms with muons, it is concluded that: $\alpha_{C\mu p} = \alpha_{Ce^-} = \alpha_{Cep}$. From using Eq. (184), Eq. (183) and Eq. (70) setting $\alpha_{C\mu p} = \alpha_{Cep}$ yields:

$$\frac{N_{\mu U}^2}{2m_\mu m_{pl}^2} \left(\frac{\hbar}{R_U c_0} \right)^3 = 2 \frac{m_e c_0 R_U}{\hbar} \frac{m_\mu m_p}{m_{pl}^2} \left(\frac{q_\mu}{q} \right)^2,$$

and reformulates to:

$$N_{\mu U} = 2 \frac{W_0(m_{e0}) \gamma_\mu W_0(m_{\mu 0}) |q_\mu|}{W_{Gh}^2 |q|}, \quad (189)$$

with: $W_{Gh} = W_{GhU}$ for stable fundamental particles, i.e. with lifetime of the particle being longer than the age of the Universe. For instable particles it is: $W_{Gh} = \frac{\hbar}{\tau_{Lx}}$, meaning that confinement and respective photon energy is given by the local sphere emerging with particle lifetime.

Expressing this as a maximum particle density allowed a picturesque result is obtained for the muon:

³⁰ This is an important fact, meaning although electron and muon are different fundamental particles in the family of leptons, they belong to a joint quantum statistic building the copper atom shell. Refer to section II.C.5 above for a theoretical explanation. The electronic and thus chemical behavior of muonic atoms in detail although must differ from the original atoms as the muon is bound closer to the atomic nucleus due to its higher mass [59].

$$n_{\mu U} \leq \frac{3}{\lambda_{Gh} \lambda_C(m_{e0}) \lambda_C(m_{\mu 0}) \gamma_{\mu}} \frac{|q_{\mu}|}{q}, \quad (190)$$

with: $\lambda_{Gh} = 2\pi R_U$ for stable fundamental particles, i.e. lifetime of particle is longer than the age of the Universe. However, for an instable particle like the muon it is: $\lambda_{Gh} = 2\pi \tau_{Lx} c_0 \geq \lambda_C(m_{\mu 0}) \gamma_{\mu}$. In the latter case confinement is given by the local sphere emerging with particle lifetime, with the minimum extend starting at the reduced relativistic Compton wavelength of the particle. This also implicates that at this point in time the maximum ghton energy will be the total relativistic energy of particle, as it is confined by itself.

Eq. (189) and Eq. (190) will also be valid for other fundamental particles (like quarks, other leptons), meaning their maximum volumetric density is defined by the product of their reduced Compton wavelength with the wavelengths of the electron and ghton representing the gravitational and the Coulombian forces, normalized to the elementary electrical charge of the electron q . In this the relativistic mass of the muon $m_x = m_{x0} \gamma_x$ must be considered so that allowed density will increase with kinetic energy of the particles, as already has been shown regarding the neutrino in the subsection above.

An interpretation for this upper limit for volumetric density is as follows: For a fundamental particle to exist in the Universe it is not only required that it can occupy a spatial extend based on its reduced Compton wavelength as derived in section II.C, but orthogonally to this also spatial extends are required for the interaction bosons for gravitation (the ghton in the Universe) and electrodynamics (the Photon related to the electron) that need space to unambiguously couple to each of the fundamental particles.

Note that the maximum density applies to the complete volume that contains a joint quantum statistic. For stable fundamental particles like the electron the entire Universe must be considered to calculate the density, i.e. there are no local maximum densities defined. This means inhomogeneities with larger densities of electrons like in solid state objects are allowed, if only the upper density limit for the entire Universe is preserved.

(d) Coulombian Repulsion and Attraction between fundamental particles

As derived above, the electrons' repulsion can be interpreted as degeneracy pressure due to more quantum energy states required than available. Due to this pressure the configuration of all electrons in the Universe tends towards an equidistant setup. With this

the total energetic minimum rooted in the principle of stationary action is realized. This principle was first formulated by J.-L. Lagrange and W. R. Hamilton and later explained by E. Noether as resulting from the symmetry of space and time – see also section II.C.5 above.

The same principle conclusively will apply to further stable elementary particles that emerged after the big bang, like the first generation up- and down quarks and the electron-neutrino, and hence their respective quantum statistics within the entire Universe.

The Coulombian repulsion even between distinct fundamental particles appearing with different numbers in the Universe can be explained by their joint multi-particle quantum statistics as described in section II.C.5.

The Fermi energy required for adding/removing a single mass particle ($N := 1$) to/from the Universe as confined in the average distance of available states d_{as} according to Eq. (23) and Eq. (50) is:

$$W_{Fr}(d_{as}) = W_{Gh}(d_{as}) \left(\frac{9\pi}{4}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} = \frac{3}{2} m c_0^2, \text{ with:}$$

$$d_{as} = \left[\frac{2(n_{Grmax}(m, R_U))^3}{\frac{4}{3}\pi R_U^3} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}}. \quad (191)$$

This result consistently confirms the maximum energy found in Eq. (60) for a mass object in a homogenous Universe. Again, gravitation as well as Coulombian energy is found to be a quantum mechanical confinement energy to apply to identical particles.

Coulombian attraction between fundamental particles can be explained by their tendency for annihilation and hence removal from respective quantum statistics in the Universe. This is also rooted in the principle of stationary action referred to above.

Two prominent cases for attraction and annihilation are described below:

- (a) Electron – Positron attraction and annihilation is the realization of a process removing both particles from the Universe. In the Penrose particle wave-picture of both particles having the same mass and hence same wavelength, if approaching to the same location these will annihilate due to destructive interference requiring that the positron exhibits a wave function phase shifted by the value of π versus the phase of the electron. The same principle is assumed to apply also for the other lepton / anti-lepton pairs, i.e. (anti-)muons, (anti-)taons.
- (b) Electron-Proton attraction first leads to

emergence of a hydrogen atom as described in the Bohr model.

Direct annihilation to a neutron at low energies is not possible since the particle's Compton wavelength of the electron is much larger than that of the (u/d) quark constituents making up the proton. However, if the electron mass is increased by a relativistic kinetic energy of $(2.16 - 0.51)MeV$ to match the rest mass of the u-quark contained in the proton, both particle waves can annihilate by destructive interference if approaching the same location, thus releasing the total energy of the relativistic electron and the u-quark being $4.32 MeV$. Further energy is needed to constitute a d-quark with the rest mass of $4.67 MeV$ to then build a neutron (u/d/d) together with the remaining d- and u-quark from the proton. As the rest energy difference between the neutron and the proton plus electron is $0.78 MeV$ this kinetic energy must be added to realize the electron-proton annihilation yielding a neutron and a neutrino, while the latter one can be neglected in the energy balance.

Beyond the attraction-annihilation/removal explanation given above, Coulombian attraction between non-identical elementary particles also follows as enforced gravitational attraction making up the electrodynamic interaction, rooted in the instability of the Heisenberg uncertainty as shown in section III.I and confirmed in the KGE/SE analysis in section II.C.5 allowing also attractive forces. This means in analogy to Eq. (158) for the gravitational attraction, the potential energy for an elementary particle with mass m and electrical charge q associated with another mass object in distance r also exhibiting charge q can be described as:

$$W_{Cpot} = \frac{q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r} = \eta_C^2 m c_0^2 \quad , \quad (192)$$

with $\eta_C(n) = \frac{\alpha_C}{n}$ while n is the integer quantum number.

Coulombian interaction forces between non-elementary mass objects must consider the total or partial neutralization due superposition of repulsive and attractive forces from the elementary particles contained, like e.g. for the neutron and proton consisting of in total three up / down quarks with their different charges.

To summarize this subsection, a standalone, fundamental electrical charge and hence

electrodynamic force is not required as such by nature, since it can be derived out of the mass and quantities of the respective fundamental particles and the total mass and size of the Universe. In this the electrodynamic force can be described as a degeneracy effect of the gravitational force, while the latter one had been explained in the EQGM already as fundamental quantum mechanical effect based on the quantized wave nature of elementary particles and their energies in the Universe as a potential well.

K. Gravitational quantum particles and matter waves

First gravitational particles were assumed by Pierre-Simon Laplace more than two centuries ago, while a quantum mechanical particle named Graviton was mentioned around the mid-20th century. In the diverse set of quantum gravity approaches the Graviton is mostly, but not always, assumed to be the exchange quantum of gravitation. However, also further particles were proposed, like Gravitino, Goldstino, Sgoldstino, Gravissskalar and Gravivektor [25].

In the EQGM each mass object has a quantized gravitational energy state – dubbed with the quasi-particle name “gravon” – and a de Broglie matter wave [26] associated. The gravitational effect is assumed to be realized via the quantum exchange particle dubbed ghoton, moving at the speed of light. For a mass object to change its gravitational energy, i.e. gravon state, ghotons must be emitted to decrease, or absorbed to increase its gravitational energy, respectively. In section II.C it is interpreted, that the ghotons make up a ghoton sea, i.e. a particle bath within the Universe, which is supported in section III.G by consideration of an Unruh acceleration.

In the duality picture the ghotons are the particles to make up gravitational waves.

Both, ghoton and gravon, quantum particle energies are inversely proportional to the confinement space, i.e. the distance between interacting mass objects. In case of interaction considered between a mass and the entire mass of the Universe this is the radius of the Universe R_U .

In the EQGM the ghoton is the exchange particle to play the role of the Graviton, while the gravon is a quasi-particle representing the matter waves associated with DE and DM. The ghoton can be concluded to be a boson from several aspects.

First, it can be directly seen out of Bohr's postulate with integer spin quantum number multiples of energy as:

$\Delta p \Delta r = \hbar n$ and with: $\Delta W = \Delta p c_0$, it results:

$$W_{Gh}(\Delta r) = n \frac{\hbar c_0}{\Delta r} \quad (193)$$

Second, it appears that ghton energy and integer multiples of it result from the gravitational vacuum energy as will be derived in the section below and is given in Eq. (196).

Third, it appeared in the gravitational Bohr model in Eq. (18) and (36), while complementing the kinetic gravitational energy, giving a first notion of a ghton bath in the Universe. In Eq. (157) a ghton bath was concluded from the quantum gravitational zero-point acceleration as an Unruh acceleration.

Fourth, the gravitational coupling parameter between the minimum possible mass in the Universe that is associated with the ghton according to Eq. (52) and the total mass of the Universe exhibits the value of one, as can be seen from Eq. (70). This means the ghton moves at the speed of light, which is only possible for a boson.

Fifth, for the ghton W_{GhU} that if it would be a fermion, its number of available states would only allow two ghtons to fit into the Universe without “excess quantization” required as for the electron, since $n_{asGhU} = 2$ as can be seen out of revisiting Eqs. (23), (50) and (52). This means apart from the bosonic ghton, there could be fermions with excess quantization and the minimum possible mass in the Universe. However, if there are any, their number would have to be small $< 10^{12}$ or higher than $> 10^{90}$ to not carry significant electrical charge values beyond $10^{-6}q$. This results from a calculation according to Eq. (188) but applied for minimum mass particles m_{minU} considering relativistic effects.

L. Fundamental energies in the Universe

(a) Appearance of gravitational energies

Along the different appearances of energies related to gravity used in the EQGM, it was found that there is an identity of the energies attached to mass in the Universe:

$$-W_{gpot}(m) = W_{gkin}(m) = m c_0^2 = \sqrt{2} \sigma_{WU} = m \gamma \sigma_a \sqrt{2} R_U = \sigma_m \sqrt{2} \gamma g_{zp} R_U.$$

³¹ The so-called Zitterbewegung can also be interpreted to be implicit in the wavefunction of a mass object as given in Eq. (78), with the part depending on time containing the product of the mass object’s relativistic energy including rest energy and time divided by Planck’s quantum of action. Hence the “Zitter-frequency” is: $\omega_z = \frac{W_0(m) + W_{kin}}{\hbar}$. Note that the rest energy is identical to self-ghoton energy of the mass object.

With:

Newton gravitational potential energy, as negative identity for the gravitational kinetic energy of the mass related to $r = R_U$ at the boarder of the Universe.

Rest energy of mass according to Einstein's Equivalence Principle, which led to use of mass and energy synonymous in the General Relativity Theory in the Energy-Momentum Tensor [3].

Quantum mechanical uncertainty zero-point energy for mass, as shown in this work. This energy can be interpreted as fluctuations on a time scale τ_{fluc} in two ways:

1. As a so called “Zitterbewegung”, a phenomenon first described in [43] for electrons. In EQGM it is found to cause zero-point acceleration for mass objects appearing as gravitational acceleration g_{zp} and being interpreted as kinetic energy fluctuations, with $\gamma = 2$:

$$\sigma_{WU} \sqrt{2} = W_{kin} = m c_0^2.$$

2. As “mass-defect energy fluctuation”, where zero-point energy is temporarily created out of mass and vice versa:

$$\sigma_{WU} \sqrt{2} = W_0 = m c_0^2.$$

Both interpretations, the Zitterbewegung³¹ and the mass defect energy fluctuation, can also go hand in hand as a kind of duality in terms of a zigzag picture for fermions with rest mass m being a coupling parameter between two wave-functions propagating with the speed of light, as described in [6]. Based on the fluctuation time their minimum spatial expanse would be the reduced Compton wavelength (see Eq. (141)), aka the relativistic gravitational Bohr radius - see Eq. (32).

To summarize, the physical parameters of mass, rest energy of mass, negative gravitational potential and attached Newtonian zero-point kinetic energy, as well as quantum zero-point energy are found to be equivalent representations to characterize gravitation in the Universe. Moreover, the zero-point kinetic energy of a mass object in the Universe is found to appear on-top of the rest energy and being invariant regarding total mass and radius of the Universe.

(b) *Energy density in a confined vacuum*

With the Heisenberg uncertainty as of Eq. (2) and the ghton defined in Eq. (19), it can be written for a relativistic mass object in the one-dimensional case in the spherical Universe with a confinement space as $x = r$:

$W_{Gh}(R_U)R_U = W_0(m)\lambda_C(m) = \hbar c_0 = 2\sigma_W\sigma_x$, with the relativistic mass object fluctuating at the speed of light:

$$\sigma_t = \frac{\sigma_x}{c_0}, \text{ and: } W_0(m) = W_{Gh}(\lambda_C(m)) \quad (194)$$

Hence, the minimum energy-expanse-product of the vacuum is a constant of nature being reflected in the Heisenberg uncertainty. This means in the wave-particle duality with two extremes a minimum possible energy can be

- a) completely delocalized in the Universe, resulting into the ghton energy “wave” for $\lambda = 2\pi R_U$
- b) completely localized in the Universe, resulting into the rest energy and the notion of a particle with a “mass”.
In this the „rest energy“ is the ghton energy of the Compton wavelength for this mass.

The analogue result is obtained from a three-dimensional approach, in terms of the minimum energy contained in a confined sphere with radius R that can be calculated by integrating over the expansive pressure contained due to Heisenberg uncertainty. Note that in this the notion of a “mass” is even not required:

$$W_{vac} = \int_{-\infty}^R P_{exp} A dr, \text{ with: } P_{exp} = \frac{\sqrt{2}\sigma_W}{\frac{4}{3}\pi r^3} \quad (195)$$

and: $A = 4\pi r^2$; $\sigma_t = \sigma_x c_0 = \frac{r}{\sqrt{2}} c_0$, yields:

$$W_{vacG}(R, n) = 3nW_{Gh}(R) = 3n \frac{\lambda_C(m)}{R} m c_0^2, \text{ with } n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (196a)$$

It shows that the ghton energy is the minimum gravitational energy of a confined vacuum, with the zero-point energy for $n = 1$. Higher energy levels in the vacuum are discretized as integer multiples n of the ghton energy. These could also be understood as waves with wavelengths of integer fractions of the confinement perimeter.

At the same time this ghton energy is the rest energy of a mass with its Compton wavelength being the confinement radius aka the self-gravitation energy of

the mass.

In analogy, the electrodynamic vacuum energy can be defined as:

$$W_{vacC}(R, n) = 3nW_{Gh}(R) \frac{\alpha_C}{\alpha_{Gep}} = 3n \frac{2R_U}{R} W_{Ph}(\lambda_C(m_e)) = 3n \frac{R_U}{R} 2m_e c_0^2 \quad (196b)$$

(d) *Duality picture of energy*

From Eq. (65) a possible interpretation for the hyperbolic gravitational potential from the mass tuple (m, M) in the Universe is, that with increasing / decreasing quantum number n the kinetic gravitational energy of mass m is gained by absorption / reduced by emission of ghtons from a ghton sea, i.e. a gravitation particle bath residing in the Universe. The gravitational kinetic energy and total ghton energies in the bath are complementary depending on n , and their product equals the rest energy value of the mass squared. This can be interpreted and written as a “duality product” representing the actual mass object (described by W_{kin}) and the matter wave (described by multiples of Universe-ghton particles). On the other side of the equation the duality energy split equaling the product of rest energy of mass m and ghton-wave energy associated with mass m in the Penrose picture [6] in terms of the standing reduced Compton wave is found:

$$[W_{gkin}][nW_{Gh}(R_U)] = \left[\sqrt{\frac{M}{M_U}} W_0(m) \right] \left[\sqrt{\frac{M}{M_U}} W_{Gh}(\bar{\lambda}_C(m)) \right]. \quad (197)$$

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The EQGM looking at the Universe as composed of quantum wells delivers qualitative and quantitative explanation approaches for effects associated with DM and DE, and even an analytical approach to nuclear and electrodynamic physics in line with observations.

It is found that gravity can be described as a quantum mechanical effect as such.

Furthermore, the quantum mechanical model as derived here can also serve to deliver a unification approach of fundamental forces for gravitation, Coulombian electrodynamics, and strong interaction on nucleons in atomic nuclei (unified GCS potential).

The total on top energy appearing in the EQGM for the Universe is: $W_{Uzp} = DE = M_U c_0^2 = (DM + VM) c_0^2 = 5.899 \cdot 10^{70} J$. The mass equivalent associated with this DE is the mass of the Universe M_U

itself, which thus is also containing the missing DM. Hence, a DM as a kind of so far unknown “physical matter” is not required here since the gravitational zero-point acceleration leading to the DE has been identified to explain the effect of observed galaxy rotation violation.

Bekenstein-Hawking entropy of the Universe is conclusively found to be based on the ratio of DE versus ghoton energy. This is equivalent to total mass of the Universe versus minimum possible mass of a particle in the Universe and as such delivering the information entropy about the mass objects contained in the Universe.

For the gravitational quantum effects that should exhibit discrete effects as discussed above, a qualitative and quantitative explanation approach for the phenomenon of redshift quantization matching with observations can be provided by the EQGM – see Appendix C.

Furthermore, the pion energy describing the strong interaction force effect in the deuteron is found to be identical to the energy of the ghoton for the deuteron describing the gravitational force.

A comprehensive summary of propositions concluded from the EQGM out of this work can be found in Appendix E.

Given the vast diversity and history of research in the field of quantum gravity done in the last decades, it must be beyond the scope of this work to discuss and assess the EQGM as compared to the variety of approaches.

Moreover, it is left for further study how the EQGM and its findings can also help to understand the evolution of the Universe and the atomic nuclei even better, from the origin and towards destination.

V. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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VI. APPENDIX

APPENDIX A. RELATIVISTIC HEISENBERG UNCERTAINTY RELATION

The Heisenberg uncertainty relation shall be described for an inertial system of the Universe (U), with the mass moving with velocity v in it, and in the inertial system of the mass object itself (m_0), where the mass is at rest. The Lorentz factor is described as: $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c_0^2}}}$. To generalize, I do not exclude any of the physical parameters from uncertainty and hence do allow variances for all of them, leading to a generic form:

$$\sigma_m \sigma_a \sigma_t \sigma_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (A1)$$

To recapitulate, the following rules from Special Relativity Theory apply for two inertial systems moving with relative velocity v to each other [44]:

Relativistic increase of inertia increases momentum and energy of the mass object observed in the inertial system of the Universe, as described by the Lorentz factor.

Time scales of the observed other inertial system appear slower, i.e. decreased (time dilation).

Length scales of the observed other inertial system appear reduced (length contraction).

Time and length scales observed within each inertial system appear unchanged, thus also velocity and acceleration within each inertial system appear unchanged.

Hence the relative velocities of inertial systems to each other are observed at the same value in both systems.

The Heisenberg uncertainty applies within both inertial systems as:

$$\sigma_{pU} \sigma_{xU} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}, \text{ and: } \sigma_{WU} \sigma_{tU} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}, \text{ as well as: } \sigma_{pmo} \sigma_{xmo} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}, \text{ and: } \sigma_{Wmo} \sigma_{tmo} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (A2)$$

The actual physical parameter and its variance are related so that Heisenberg uncertainty set as equation matches the ground state $n = 1$ of Bohr's postulate:

$$pr \equiv \hbar n, \text{ equals: } \sigma_p \sigma_x = \frac{\hbar}{2}, \text{ hence: } \sigma_p = \frac{p}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ and: } \sigma_x = \frac{x}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ with: } x = r \quad (A3)$$

Consequently, for energy and time uncertainty it is:

$$\sigma_W = \frac{W}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ and: } \sigma_t = \frac{t}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (\text{A4})$$

Thus, for the inertial system of the Universe the momentum, the effective inertia and kinetic energy of the mass object resting in its inertial system (mo) must be adapted by the Lorentz factor. The uncertainty of energy can be rooted in the rest energy or in the kinetic energy:

$$\sigma_{pU} = \sigma_{mU} \sigma_{aU} \sigma_{tU} = \frac{p_U}{\sqrt{2}}, \text{ and}$$

$$\sigma_{WU} = \sigma_{mU} \sigma_{aU} \sigma_{xU} = \frac{W_0}{\sqrt{2}} \quad \text{or} \quad = \frac{W_{kin}}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (\text{A5})$$

For the energy and momentum, the relativistic relations must be taken, note that relativistic energy contains the rest energy, while momentum is zero at rest:

$$W_U = m_U c_0^2 = m_{mo} \gamma c_0^2 = W_0 + W_{kinU}$$

$$= m_{mo} c_0^2 + m_{mo} (\gamma - 1) c_0^2, \text{ with: } m_{mo} = m. \quad (\text{A6})$$

Furthermore an Eq. (A7) is:

$$p_U = \sqrt{\left(\frac{W_U}{c_0}\right)^2 - (m_U c_0)^2} = m_{mo} \gamma v_U = m_U a_U t_U.$$

For the inertial system of the mass object (mo) the time and length scale of the Universe must be adapted by the Lorentz factor:

$$\sigma_{p_{mo}} = \sigma_{m_{mo}} \sigma_{a_{mo}} \sigma_{t_{mo}}, \text{ and: } \sigma_{x_{mo}} = \sigma_{x_U} \gamma^{-1}. \quad (\text{A8})$$

$$\sigma_{W_{mo}} = \sigma_{m_{mo}} \sigma_{a_{mo}} \sigma_{x_{mo}}, \text{ and: } \sigma_{t_{mo}} = \sigma_{t_U} \gamma. \quad (\text{A9})$$

APPENDIX B. EXPANSION BASED ON FRIEDMAN EQUATION

I set up the Friedman equation [45] for a flat Universe according to the Standard Model of Cosmology (Λ -Cold Dark Matter-CDM), while considering the on-top gravitational zero-point acceleration as derived in the EQGM. Hence mass density ρ_U and the expansive pressure P_{exp} are assumed as:

$$\rho_U(r) = \frac{M_U}{(4/3)\pi r^3} \text{ and: } P_{exp}(r) = \frac{-W_{zpu}}{(4/3)\pi r^3},$$

while: $W_{zpu} = M_U c_0^2$. (B1)

With $a(r)$ being the scale factor for the radius of the Universe and $a = 1$ for the current state: $a(r) = \frac{r}{R_U}$.

The Friedman equation with \ddot{a} being the second time derivative for the scale factor $a(r)$, this means normalized acceleration can be written at $r = R_U$ as:

$$\ddot{a}(r) = a(r) \left[\frac{-4\pi G}{3} \left(\rho_U(r) + \frac{3P_{exp}(r)}{c_0^2} \right) \right] - \frac{g_{zp}}{R_U} = \frac{3c_0^2}{2R_U^2},$$

thus: $\ddot{a}(R_U) = 6.921 \cdot 10^{-37} s^{-2}$. (B2)

Delivering the first derivative of the Hubble parameter with respect to time at $r = R_U$, i.e., for the scale parameter at $a = 1$ yields:

$$\dot{H}_0 = \frac{\dot{a}(R_U)}{a} - H_0^2, \text{ hence:}$$

$$\dot{H}_0 = -3.924 \cdot 10^{-3} s^{-2}. \quad (\text{B3})$$

APPENDIX C. APPROACH TO REDSHIFT QUANTIZATION

With the EQGM an explanation for the redshift quantization phenomenon in the spectrum of hydrogen atoms observed in some galaxies and quasar structures, which is not yet understood and partially still disputed, can presumably now be provided in terms of a quantum gravitational effect.

More than half a century ago, astronomical observations of electromagnetic spectrums – e.g. the 21 cm hydrogen line - delivered redshift results with different peak values and discretization increments in the order of magnitude $\Delta z = 0.001 \dots 3.6$, with $\Delta z = 1.95$, as well as $\Delta z = 0.061 \dots 0.063$, and periodic multiples being prominent values often found – see [24], [47], [48], [49], [50]. The redshift quantization is hypothesized to be intrinsic to galaxies and quasars, but with origins unknown so far, thus not related to cosmological redshift due to Hubble expansion.

To obtain such significant redshift values from quantized gravitational fields, the hydrogen atoms observed must be moving with fractions of the speed of light, i.e. close to massive objects M , if not even black holes. Furthermore, such obvious discretization can only occur at low quantum numbers, since otherwise continuum effects for the redshift would apply. The combination of these two aspects leads to the conclusion that the radius – see Eq. (32) - for the free hydrogen atom mass m_n observed around M must be in the range of some femtometers.

Hence, a possible candidate for M could be Primordial Black Holes (PBH) emerged out of fluctuations in the early Universe, and as described by S. Hawking in [51]. Such black holes would have to exhibit a minimum mass according to their Schwarzschild radius to be equal or larger than the reduced Compton wavelength of the particles - i.e. as related to their relativistic energy including rest energy - constituting such black hole. These constituents could be neutrons and/or protons, or pairs of them, thus deuterons. In the latter case this allows for less minimum mass required to build a PBH as compared to protons/neutrons alone. Hawking also concluded that these objects may carry of up to $Z < 30$ Coulomb charges. Thus, the mass of

such PBH would be: $M_{pbhd} = \frac{\lambda_C(m_{con})c_0^2}{2G} = 6.721 \cdot 10^{10} kg$, with the effective constituent particle mass $m_{con} = m_n + m_p - \Delta m_{md} + \Delta m_C = 2.107 m_n$, i.e. made up by the mass of the deuteron containing the neutron and proton minus the mass defect of their binding energy $\Delta m_{md} = 2.222 MeV c_0^{-2}$, plus the mass equivalent of the potential Coulomb energy allocated to the PBH for an average charge assumed of $Z = 15$: $\Delta m_C = \left(\frac{Zq^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\lambda_C(m_p)} \right) c_0^{-2}$.

With this the reduced Compton wavelength of the constituent mass aka the Schwarzschild radius of M_{pbhd} is $0.1 fm$.

The intrinsic redshift of mass objects moving with velocity v in the inertial system of a galaxy - without consideration of the recessional aka cosmological redshift of the galaxy in the Universe - can be found for example in [24]: $z_{int} = z_t + z_g$ for transverse Doppler redshift, and $z_{inr} = z_r + z_g$ for radial Doppler redshift, respectively, while for each the gravitational aka Einstein redshift z_g comes on top. With $z_g = (\gamma - 1)$ and $z_t = (\gamma - 1)$, while γ being the Lorentz factor - see Appendix A, and $z_r =$

$$\sqrt{\frac{1 + \frac{v}{c_0}}{1 - \frac{v}{c_0}}} - 1.$$

To calculate the redshift, Eq. (31) is used for the hydrogen atom with mass m_n in the hyperbolic gravitational potential of charged PBHs with $M_x = jM_{pbhd}$ and $j \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$W_{kr}(n, j, m) = mc_0^2[\gamma(n, j, m) - 1], \text{ and:} \quad (C1)$$

$$\gamma(n, j, m) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\left| 1 + \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{j^2 m M_{pbhd} c}{n m_p l^2} \right)^2} \right|}}.$$

In this the absolute value is taken from the Lorentz factor to obtain a real meaning from this, since otherwise for quantum states within the Schwarzschild radius un-physical complex values would be calculated.

The radii can be calculated from Eq. (32) above:

$$r_U = \frac{r_S(jM_{pbhd})}{\left| 1 - \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{j^2 m M_{pbhd} c}{n m_p l^2} \right)^2} \right|}, \quad (C2)$$

Thus, the gravitational ground-state radius for hydrogen atoms at a PBH with M_{pbhd} is $0.831 fm$.

It is important to understand, that the radius of the

hydrogen atom as such including its electron - i.e. of which photon emission redshifts from the Coulombian system $(m_e; m_p)$ are observed - is five orders of magnitude larger. Hence while the proton in the core of the hydrogen atom can be located within the Schwarzschild-radius of the PBH for $n < n_S$, and thus cannot be observed from the inertial system of the Universe, its shell electron is located far outside the Schwarzschild radius of the gravitational system $(m_p; M_{pbhd})$ and thus its excitations and redshift behavior can be observed in the Universe. In Eq. (C1) the quantum states inside the PBH that have hence to be considered do result into a negative radicand for the inner root term, so that the absolute value from the complex number result arising must be taken to calculate the kinetic energy.

Regarding the Coulombian interaction and kinetic energy for the hydrogen atom, given the gravitational radii above it is concluded that the entire neutral hydrogen atom will reside in the Coulombian ground-state of the charged PBH since the respective radius is several orders of magnitude larger than the gravitational radius. Thus, the Coulombian interaction will play no role related to the redshift quantization.

Eq. (C2) reveals another property of this PBH: In addition to its minimum required mass M_{pbhd} , this is also the maximum value for mass, if the PBH was grown out of nucleons and/or hydrogen. This is since the ground state $n = 1$ and related minimum radius for hydrogen atoms and H_2 molecules being gravitationally attracted by the PBH is the lowest possible. Hence, the attracted atoms or molecules cannot fall into and grow the mass of the PBH further but will orbit around it instead.

This gives rise to the assumption, that only integer multiples of the PBH mass appear in some regions of the galaxies and quasar objects, once PBHs with exact mass M_{pbhd} do attract each other to build larger black holes.

If in galaxies the value ranges from $j = 1..j_{max}$ (number of merged PBHs attracting hydrogen atoms whose spectra are observed) and $n = 1..n_{max}$ (gravitational quantum states occupied by these hydrogen atoms around the black hole) may vary, different sets of discretized redshifts may be observed. Fig. C1a and C1b display the transverse and radial Doppler redshifts including gravitational redshift for hydrogen atoms occupying all quantum levels of $1..20$ with equal probability in the quantized field of black holes and with equally distributed mass values of integer multiples from $1..10^4 M_{pbhd}$ PBH mass constituted out of deuterons and with 15 Coulomb

charges each³². Tab. C1a and C1b contain the redshift values for the eight lowest and quantum levels and PBH mass multiples of the black hole, respectively.

FIG. C1a. Relative probability of transverse Doppler (circles) and radial Doppler (crosses) redshift values z and including gravitational Einstein redshift for hydrogen atoms occupying quantum levels of up to $n_{\max} = 20$ in the gravitational fields of black holes with masses of up to $10^4 M_{pbhdc}$ and a Coulomb charge of $Z = 15$ constituted of deuterons. The bin width for z is 0.001.

FIG. C1b. Same as in FIG E1a but with a focus on and zoom-in to the left-hand side of the redshift z -axis.

From Eq. (C2) with the mass of hydrogen atoms a characteristic value of $z_{\text{int}} = 0.063$ is very prominent³³, because it appears for all combinations (j, n) with $j = n$ so that the quotient is $j/n = 1$. This is the most common value for the quotient in Eq. (C1) out of the linear discrete set of integers – see also Figures C1a and C1b. Moreover, integer values of the quotient do also appear more prominent than other values since they have a periodic appearance as compared to non-integer fractions. This may explain the observed periodicity of $\Delta z = 0.063$ described in

³² Due to Hawking radiation black holes will evaporate after a certain time, if no infalling matter is compensating the loss of mass. Such complete evaporation within the time up to the age of the current Universe may happen for $M_{pbh} < 4..5 \cdot 10^{11} \text{kg}$ [52], i.e. $j < 10$. In this work the evaporation process is explained by emission of ghotons – see Eq. (152).

³³ In the initial publication of Karlsson on „Possible Quantization of Quasar Redshifts” [48] the characteristic observed peak values are stated as $z = 0.061, 0.06$, while calculating from his fit formula $(1 - z_i)/(1 + z_{i+1}) = 1.227$, and with $z_1 = 1.956$, this results to: $z_2 = 1.409, z_3 = 0.963, z_4 = 0.6, z_5 = 0.304$, and $z_6 = 0.063$.

some of the literature – see for example [47], [49].

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	0.0628	0.4685	0.9335	1.0199	1.0863	1.1398	1.1841	1.2218
2	0.0145	0.0628	0.1681	0.4685	0.8791	0.9335	0.9798	1.0199
3	0.0063	0.0262	0.0628	0.1236	0.2283	0.4685	0.8586	0.8983
4	0.0035	0.0145	0.0336	0.0628	0.1054	0.1681	0.2673	0.4685
5	0.0022	0.0091	0.0211	0.0386	0.0628	0.0956	0.1399	0.2019
6	0.0016	0.0063	0.0145	0.0262	0.0421	0.0628	0.0894	0.1236
7	0.0012	0.0046	0.0105	0.019	0.0303	0.0448	0.0628	0.0852
8	0.0009	0.0035	0.008	0.0145	0.0229	0.0336	0.0468	0.0628

TAB. C1a. Transverse Doppler redshift values for hydrogen atoms including gravitational redshift at the first 8 quantum levels (vertical direction) with black holes exhibiting multiples 1..8 of PBH mass (horizontal direction) and as displayed in Fig. C1b.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	0.3154	1.1919	2.0066	2.1512	2.2616	2.35	2.423	2.4847
2	0.1349	0.3154	0.5867	1.1919	1.9146	2.0066	2.0843	2.1512
3	0.086	0.1887	0.3154	0.4805	0.7196	1.1919	1.8799	1.9471
4	0.0631	0.1349	0.2177	0.3154	0.4343	0.5867	0.8014	1.1919
5	0.0499	0.105	0.1665	0.2359	0.3154	0.4084	0.5205	0.6623
6	0.0412	0.086	0.1349	0.1887	0.2484	0.3154	0.3918	0.4805
7	0.0351	0.0728	0.1134	0.1573	0.2051	0.2575	0.3154	0.3802
8	0.0306	0.0631	0.0978	0.1349	0.1747	0.2177	0.2644	0.3154

TAB. C1b. Radial Doppler redshift values for hydrogen atoms including gravitational redshift at the first 8 quantum levels (vertical direction) with black holes exhibiting multiples 1..8 of PBH mass (horizontal direction) and as displayed in Fig. C1b.

For hydrogen atoms, the characteristic value around $z_{\text{int}} = 1.96$ allows to directly conclude on the average mass multiples of merged PBHs. This value indicates around 10^4 PBHs merged in average. For the number of merged PBHs towards infinity it would result $\gamma \rightarrow 0$, hence: $z_{\text{int}} \rightarrow 2$, since $z_g \rightarrow 1$ and $z_t \rightarrow 1$. Following this mathematical result based on the SRT approach, the interpretation of the Lorentz factor to

strive towards zero is that the hydrogen nucleus would vanish in the PBH. To conserve energy, this would require setting free radiation within the PBH by annihilation, or creation of other particles. Note that, if the GRT/Schwarzschild approach with Eq. (45) would be applied to the PBH and hydrogen atom, the Lorentz factor and thus redshift would approach very high but finite values towards the ground-state $n \rightarrow 1$.

Obviously, a plain modeling based on the GRT/Schwarzschild approach will not exhibit the culmination of prominent redshift values around 1.96 and 3.6, hypothetically since other as with the SRT model particle annihilation is not implicated.

For the number of merged PBHs towards infinity it will result:

$$z_{inr} \rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{1+\sqrt{3}/2}{1-\sqrt{3}/2}} + z_g = 3.732, \text{ since with } z_g \rightarrow 1 \text{ and } \gamma \rightarrow 2 \text{ it is: } v \rightarrow c_0 \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}.$$

For higher numbers of occupied quantum level states n , up to $n_{\max} \rightarrow \infty$, more redshift values in the range of $z \rightarrow 0$ will appear. Hence also in galaxies with high hydrogen gas density the discretized redshift with prominent values as shown in Fig. C1 could be observed.

Furthermore, since in the redshift formula Eqs. (C1) and (C2) the product (mM_{pbhd}) is relevant, larger characteristic values for z will result for the redshifted spectrum received from larger atoms observed in the gravitational field of the black holes. For example, the prominent values for transverse Doppler including gravitational redshift for OH molecules would be at 1.416, for CO₂ at 1.61, and for H₂ at 0.467, respectively³⁴.

To summarize, the EQGM provides a qualitative and quantitative explanation for the redshift quantization phenomenon as being rooted in quantum gravity and depending on specific setups of galaxies observed regarding their gas densities and PBH accumulations. The approach delivers analytical derivations for discretization in line with prominent peak values observed. In this it also reveals an indication for the existence and pivotal role of Primordial Black Holes (PBH) in the Universe.

Note: The procedure scripts used for calculation of

redshift quantization can be obtained from the author upon request.

APPENDIX D. MASS PARTICLES AS DARK MATTER?

To determine quantum state occupancy and degree of degeneracy³⁵ indicated by Fermi energy as compared to the depth of the homogeneous Universe parabolic quantum well, the size of the smallest elementary mass particle(s) and their volume(s) in the Universe must be known as well. As can be seen for the artificial case of a Universe with Planck-mass as elementary particles, these would be far from degeneracy:

$$W_{FPl} = 4.140 \cdot 10^{-32} J, \text{ versus:}$$

$$W_{potU} = \frac{1}{2} m_{Pl} c_0^2 = 9.78 \cdot 10^8 J, \text{ with:}$$

$$N_{Pl} = \frac{M_U}{m_{Pl}} = 2.731 \cdot 10^{61}.$$

An elementary mass particle would have to fill all available quantum states in the Universe to cause degenerate matter pressure and thus drive expansion of the Universe, as initially described in [21].

With baryonic mass observed [11] and Eq. (51) one can calculate mass and volume of such particle (X) required if it would have to make up missing DM with $\Omega_{DM} = \Omega_M - \Omega_b = 0.315 - 0.049 = 0.266$.

$W_{FX} = \frac{1}{2} m_X c_0^2$ would be required, yielding:

$$m_X = \left(\frac{2\hbar\pi}{c_0} \right)^{\frac{3}{4}} \left(\frac{9}{4} M_U \frac{\Omega_{DM}}{\pi^2 R_U^3} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}. \quad (D1)$$

This delivers $m_X = 8.233 \cdot 10^{-39} kg$ and

$$N_X = \frac{M_U \Omega_{DM}}{m_X} = 1.906 \cdot 10^{91}.$$

Thus, the corresponding rest energy, average kinetic energy and black body radiation temperature of the particle would be: $W_X = m_X c_0^2 = 4.619 meV$, $W_{kinm} = \frac{3}{5} W_{FX} = 1.386 meV$, and $T_X = 10.719 K$.

A candidate for this is the electron-neutrino with yet unknown, but smallest mass of all elementary particles in the Universe known so far. It is assumed to have the highest particle density in the Universe. However, since its temperature in the observed Cosmic Neutrino Background (CNB) considering all 6 Neutrino flavors is only 1.945 K [11] and its appearance is assumed

³⁴ However, if molecules are attracted by a PBH, it must be assumed that one or more of their atoms' nuclei are captured while their shell electrons still relate to the respective nuclei being far outside the PBH event horizon.

³⁵ An alternative formulation for degeneracy is that mass object distance be smaller than the corresponding de Broglie wavelength of the mass object, which is far from being the case for average nucleon densities in the current Universe and any mass objects larger than nucleons.

“only” some billion times higher ($n_n = 334 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $N_n = 1.22 \cdot 10^{89}$) [57] than the number of nucleons in the Universe, it can contribute less than one percentage point to missing DM.

To conclude, to date no elementary particle could be identified as a candidate to explain extra mass required as DM.

APPENDIX E. SUMMARY OF PROPOSITIONS CONCLUDED

This Appendix contains the set of propositions out of the EQGM regarding the origin and relation of key laws of Nature.

Proposition 1: Duality properties in Nature: A particle as “mass” versus “matter wave” can be explained by the Penrose picture [6]. In this the reduced Compton wavelength $\tilde{\lambda}_C(m)$ of a “standing matter wave” with mass as a coupling factor, in relativistic view (i.e. considering its rest energy), is the minimum possible spatial expanse that is required for this mass to exist. Hence an interpretation for the notion of “mass” is: “Mass” is characterizing minimum possible spatial expanse of confined energy.

Proposition 2: Origin of uncertainty: The Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle is a consequence of the duality of mass (see Proposition 1), with the Compton wavelength being the minimum size to which spatial expanse a mass can be determined. Note that the Penrose picture [6] hence allows for a deterministic interpretation of quantum uncertainty:

$$\sigma_p \sigma_x = \frac{mc_0}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\tilde{\lambda}_C(m)}{\sqrt{2}} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}, \text{ and}$$

$$\sigma_W \sigma_t = \frac{mc_0^2}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\tilde{\lambda}_C(m)}{\sqrt{2}c_0} \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad (\text{E1})$$

The measurement problem in quantum mechanics thus can be interpreted to be caused by the finite spatial expand of mass objects in terms of their Compton wavelength as well as the influence of the measurement apparatus in the measurement process. Hence, no collapse of wavefunction by measurement needs to be assumed, but the actual effective value as such does result from the concrete phase and amplitude from the wavefunction by the actual physical interaction and hence will differ due to the very short time constant in the periodic alternation of the time-depended part of the wavefunction. Thus, this Zitterbewegung can never be resolved and followed in a measurement, as to sample it the significant energy required from an appropriately short sample pulse would interfere and change the energy of the measurement object massively.

Proposition 3: Origin of mass-energy equivalence: The “rest” energy of a mass from Einstein mass-energy equivalence results from the Penrose picture [6] as a relativistic kinetic quantum fluctuation energy of a mass particle and its reduced Compton wavelength matter wave (see Proposition 1).

Proposition 4: Origin of (self-) gravitation of mass: The rest energy of a mass with radius r is also identical to the self-ghoton energy of this mass. The confinement radius r for the ghton is the reduced Compton wavelength, which is also the ultra-relativistic gravitational Bohr radius found in this work:

$$W_0 = mc_0^2 \equiv \frac{\hbar c_0}{\tilde{\lambda}_C(m)} = W_{Gh}(r_{gBr}). \quad (\text{E2})$$

Note, that (E2) also follows directly out of the Heisenberg uncertainty as given in (E1).

Proposition 5: Quantum gravitational fluctuations in the Universe:

a) For a mass object in the Universe, the ratio of its quantum fluctuation energy to its fluctuation radius is identical to the ratio of its rest energy to the diameter of the Universe – see Eq. (140):

$$\frac{W_{ftuc}}{r_{ftuc}} = \frac{W_0}{2R_U} \quad (\text{E3})$$

b) The theoretical minimum radius of the Universe – see Eq. (54) - is identical to the quantum gravitational fluctuation radius of a Planck mass in the Universe – see Eq. (138):

$$R_{U00} = \frac{\hbar}{4M_U c_0} = \frac{\tilde{\lambda}_C(M_U)}{4} = r_{ftuc}(m_{Pl}) = 1.480 \cdot 10^{-97} m \quad (\text{E4})$$

Proposition 6: Quantization of gravitation: The gravitational energy of a mass object in the Universe is quantized proportional to multiples of the gravitational Bohr radius, i.e. the reduced Compton wavelength of this mass object, within the distance between two mass objects.

The minimum spatial extend of a mass object observed from the inertial system (U) is:

$$\Delta r_m(m) = \tilde{\lambda}_C(m\gamma) = \frac{\hbar}{m\gamma v} \quad (\text{E5})$$

Hence the distance between two mass objects can in principle never become zero since $v < c_0$ is finite, and so is γ and the gravitational energy that can be gained and can thus never end in an observed singularity.

Proposition 7: Identity of strong interaction force and gravitational force: The residual strong interaction force exchange particle in the deuteron, the pion, is

identical to the gravitational exchange particle, the ghton of the deuteron – See Eq. (168).

Proposition 8: The Coulombian / electrodynamic fundamental interaction can be described as a degenerated quantum gravitational many-body interaction, and hence can be unified with gravitation.

Proposition 9: Homogeneity of space and time is the cause requiring the interaction between particles: The root for the unified quantum gravitational, Coulombian / electrodynamic and strong (qGCS) interaction bases on the principle of stationary action initially introduced in classical physics by J.-L. Lagrange and W. R. Hamilton. According to E. Noether, this can be concluded as a fundamental law originating from the homogeneity of space and time thus causing the conservation laws for energy and momentum - see for example pages 489 and 665 in [6]. In this work an immanent instability for kinetic energy striving towards extreme values contained in many particle systems was concluded out of the KGE/SE. From conservation of energy this must be caused by a complementary *unified qGCS potential* (energy).

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